

interstore

D4.1 - New generation EMS for HEMS, HESS and flexibility management report

WP4 - Multiservice and Flexibility Monetisation

**T4.1 - New generation EMS for HEMS,
HESS and flexibility management**

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Full Form
EMS	Energy Management System
HEMS	Home Energy Management System
HESS	Hybrid Energy Storage Systems
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
BESS	Battery Energy Storage Systems
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
NATS	NATS Messaging Structure
PV	Photovoltaic
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
HPP	Hydro Power Plants
DSO	Distribution System Operator
SoC	State of Charge
SoH	State of Health
PID	Proportional-Integral-Derivative
mFRR	Manual Frequency Restoration Reserve
UCAP	Ultracapacitors
SoF	State of Function
COP	Coefficient of Performance
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
LTDH	Low Temperature District Heating
FTM	Front-of-the-Meter
BTM	Behind-the-Meter
EVSE	Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment
V2G	Vehicle-to-Grid
VPP	Virtual Power Plant
API	Application Programming Interface
LPC	Legacy Protocol Converter
RT	Real-Time
GFM	Grid Forming

GFL	Grid Following
ATS	Auto Synchronization
TLBMC	Triple Layered Business Model Canvas
HyDEMS	Hybrid Distributed Energy Management System

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction.....	10
1.1	Project's objectives.....	10
1.2	Task 4.1 goals and results.....	11
1.3	Task inputs and relations.....	12
1.4	Structure of deliverable.....	12
2	Flexibility Management Platform.....	14
2.1	Interoperability toolkit.....	14
2.1.1	Development steps.....	14
2.1.2	Time plan of development.....	15
2.2	Connecting to the open data space.....	16
2.2.1	Development steps.....	16
2.2.2	Time plan of development.....	17
2.3	Hybridisation tools (deviation fighter, ramping, SoC).....	18
2.3.1	Development steps.....	18
2.3.2	Time plan of development.....	21
2.4	Market Arbitrage tool adaptation.....	21
2.4.1	Development steps.....	21
2.4.2	Time plan of development.....	23
2.5	Energy Community toolkit.....	23
2.5.1	Development steps.....	24
2.5.2	Time plan of development.....	25
3	Hybrid Distributed Energy Management System.....	26
3.1	Interoperability toolkit.....	26
3.1.1	Communication interface deployment.....	27
3.1.2	Hybridization tool.....	27
3.1.3	State of Function (SoF) tool development.....	28
3.2	Service provision of the EMS in different modes.....	33
3.2.1	Auto synchronization and grid forming (GFM DER1) test.....	34
3.2.2	Grid following (GFL - DER2 FS4G).....	35
3.2.3	Firming and frequency service with renewable profile.....	36
4	Home Energy Management System.....	40
4.1	Price and emission Incentive retrieval and incorporation.....	41
4.2	Forecasting Services adaptation to be applied to CapWatt Building.....	42
4.3	Load optimization with dispatch recommendation.....	43
4.4	Web Application as a stand-alone tool.....	44
4.4.1	Key Functionalities of the Web Application.....	44
5	Multi-physics Energy Management System.....	47

5.1	Multi-physics energy management concept	47
5.1.1	Non-functional requirements.....	47
5.1.2	Energy management concept	48
5.2	Interoperability implementation.....	49
5.3	Operational optimization	51
6	EV hybrid distributed Energy Management System	55
6.1	Interoperability toolkit.....	55
6.1.1	Development steps	55
6.1.2	Time plan of development	57
6.2	Flexibility service Implementation	57
6.2.1	New entities definition in EMS.....	58
6.2.2	Calculation of Flexibility provision	61
6.2.3	Integration with "solcast" for solar production prediction	61
6.2.4	Algorithm development	61
6.2.5	Command manager	64
6.2.6	Feedback and monitoring	65
7	Conclusions	66

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The InterSTORE project is structured around two pillars of development. The first pillar is developing tools and protocols to ensure seamless communication between different energy assets, using IEEE2030.5 communication protocol and NATS messaging structure. The second pillar is enhancing the ability to manage and monetize flexibility in energy systems through advanced EMS solutions.

The later was of particular interest in work package 4 and task 4.1, where project partners focused on upgrading existing Energy Management Systems (EMS) to support integration of Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) and improve performance, thereby contributing to the overall efficiency and resilience of the energy grid. Among various segments of DERs, connection of Hybrid Energy Storage Systems (HESS) was among the main project's objectives. HESS segment encompasses batteries, heat pumps, renewable energy sources (RES), electric vehicles (EVs), and loads.

Flexibility Management Platform

The Flexibility Management Platform developed by CyberGrid developed steps to achieve native communication via IEEE2030.5 over NATS and connection to Open Data Space. Additionally, the platform incorporates tools such as the State of Charge (SoC) manager, deviation fighter, and ramping manager to optimize battery performance. Finally, Market Arbitrage Tool and Energy Community Toolkit are the essential components in optimizing energy both internally and externally (on the market).

Hybrid Distributed Energy Management System

The Hybrid Distributed Energy Management System (HyDEMS) developed by HESStec is designed to optimize the operation of HESS and DERs. Key features include the Interoperability Toolkit, which ensures robust interaction between various energy components and compliance with IEEE2030.5 standards and Communication Interface Deployment to facilitate seamless communication with different control architectures. The Hybridization Tool and State of Function (SoF) as the key advances of the interoperable toolkit in this project, optimize the performance of hybrid energy storage systems and standardize the evaluation of energy storage systems.

Home Energy Management System

The Home Energy Management System (HEMS) was upgraded to incorporate hybrid battery dispatch and developed a web application for broader use. Key functionalities include incorporating market signals and environmental impact data. This is achieved through Price and Emission Incentive retrieval, predicting energy demand and optimizing battery dispatch with Forecasting, all already existing services in the HEMS. The goal was to reduce energy supply costs and minimizing environmental impact via Load Optimization, while considering battery degradation. The interface provides the ability for interactive simulations and performance visualizations through the Web Application.

Multi-physics Energy Management System

The Multi-physics Energy Management System integrates DERs, specifically electric heat pumps, to couple thermal and electrical energy domains. The system aims to enhance energy autarky and optimize power injection/consumption. Key components include addressing versatility, dynamic adaptability, and computational performance through Concept Development, using IEEE2030.5 and NATS network for seamless communication via Interoperability Implementation, and enhancing energy autarky and optimizing power injection/consumption through Operational Optimization.

EV Hybrid Distributed Energy Management System

The EV Hybrid Distributed Energy Management System developed by Enel X focuses on integrating diverse assets using IEEE2030.5 over NATS and optimizing energy consumption. Key components include integrating diverse assets using IEEE2030.5 over NATS through the Interoperability Toolkit and managing DERs and optimizing energy consumption via Flexibility Service Implementation.

1 Introduction

At present the European energy needs are covered by a small number of utility operators, which provide vast amounts of energy in a centralised manner. From these resources the energy is delivered to consumers via complex distribution system. However, this is rapidly changing due to increasing number of Distributed Energy Resources (DER), which is a term used to describe small technologies that produce, store and manage energy [1]. These distributed resources are challenging the existing system as the electrical infrastructure was not build with the intent to have significant production in the lowest branches of distribution. Moreover, this production tends to come from renewables, which are known for their changing level of production over time. For the moment current system and restrictions keep everything in balance but with growing number of DERs this will become increasingly more challenging. For instance, the capacity sum of renewables has doubled since 2010 (In 2023, renewable energy capacity in Europe amounted to 785.8 gigawatts compared to 322.1 gigawatts in 2010) [2] [3]. Regardless, the pressing issue due to rising number of DER pushes current system away from the use cases for which it was designed. Such a drift can cause the system to experience frequent failures which could prompt consumers to disconnect from the main grid in turn rising the maintenance cost per capita for the smaller number that remain. Such hikes in electricity prices could in turn prompt more to leave the main grid, leaving it in a “death spiral”. On the positive side greater use of DERs could improve resource efficiency, increase energy system resilience, and give individuals and communities a stronger role in decarbonisation, which is aligned well with EU goal of carbon neutrality until 2050 [4].

1.1 Project's objectives

Regardless of the pros and cons the future trend remains the same: the electrical system as we know it is changing fast and will leave us no options but to adapt to the new reality. InterSTORE project was designed to help bridge differences between current capabilities of the system and the arising needs. These so called “bridges” all strive to increase interoperability of the DER, in particular Battery Energy Storage systems (BESS). One way is by developing new and improved options to monitor and control assets, via IEEE2030.5 communication protocol [5] using NATS [6] messaging structure as data layer. This was already developed and published [7]. It can be explored on project GitHub page [8] or Docker hub [9]. We can briefly mention that said developments include client/server libraries, legacy protocol converters (which enable translation between different protocols) and testing procedures (to validate correctness of the installed IEEE2030.5 protocol).

As targeting only asset-level communication itself will not bring sought-after results InterSTORE and this work package in particular focus also on upgrading and enhancing systems that operate the assets. This is a vital step in transition of electricity energy sector as Energy Management System (EMS) usually represents the first step in aggregating, monitoring and controlling individual assets. Therefore, EMS has a huge impact on energy output of the assets in the brother energy system. As the project focuses on upgrading existing EMSs, partners of the project presented their systems and step-by-step plan on how to improve the systems.

Another approach to improving system interoperability is by increasing it's ability to share data about current, past and future states. Such improved data exchange is important as based on quality data local and state-wide systems can model the changes, which growing number of DER bring. To address these, partners have expanded the data connector developed in Int:net [10] project. Based on this novel version of open data spaces, which too can be found on GitHub [8] and Docker [9] the partners included in this task will share relevant data among ourselves.

1.2 Task 4.1 goals and results

Task 4.1 focuses on upgrading the existing EMSs the partners are using to support greater interoperability in electrical energy system. This includes integration of Hybrid Energy Storage Systems (HESS), which is a term that refers to batteries, heat pumps, renewable energy sources (RES), electric vehicles (EVs), and loads, to function as conventional battery energy storage systems with enhanced performance. Such a goal already greatly contributes toward making the electrical energy system more flexible, in particular on the low-voltage grids where active participations of such assets reduces overloads and extends their longevity [11]. In support of such operations partners developed various tools and approaches on how to best handle the connected HESS assets. To showcase applicability of EMSs and their specialised tools in a variety of diverse use cases in low-voltage grids work package 4 in InterSTORE project gathered 5 EMS that work on different segments of electrical grid. Here are the aforementioned EMS and their field of operation:

- Flexibility Management Platform focuses on offering balancing services aggregated from HESS and other DERs.
- Hybrid Distributed Energy Management System seamlessly integrates and optimizes distributed energy storage (DES), with the objective to enable the provision of a stacked pool of multiple flexibility services to grid operators.
- Home Energy management system (HEMS) optimizes produced and consumed energy inside households as well as integrates variety of HEMS.
- Residential Power Management System or Multi-physics Energy Management System is an advanced interoperable flexibility optimization in residential and/or commercial buildings.
- Electric vehicle (EV) hybrid distributed Energy Management System as the name suggests work in the segment of EV charging stations and their optimal performance, which increases customer satisfaction.

As the technical developments of the respective EMS systems are not showcasing interoperability by themselves, they will be tested in pilot environments of InterSTORE project, which will happen in later stages of the project. Like EMSs the 4 pilots are diverse and cover different segments. On the Figure 1 we can observe where and what each pilot will be focusing on. The fields range from EV charging fleets, residential buildings to industrial sites and energy communities.

Figure 1 Four pilot sites in InterSTORE.

1.3 Task inputs and relations

WP4 is situated in the middle of the InterSTORE project with close ties to work packages before and after it. Work packages 1 and 2 are used as inputs, work package 3 progresses in parallel with some tasks supporting each other. Lastly WP5 will demonstrate the new approaches based on the results of WP4 and others. The detailed presentation of WPs connections can be observed on Figure 2.

Figure 2 Workflow in InterSTORE project among WPs.

T4.1 is connected with work package 1, as we take the specification and initial plan of development for each EMS, that are described in D1.4 [7]. From the same work package we also relate to specification on new interoperable communication protocol IEEE2030.5 over NATS saved in D1.3 [7], which was then developed in T2.1 [7] and T2.2. [7] The code to the software was stored on InterSTORE GitHub [8] and Docker [9] websites. The output of this task are new generation EMS that are going to be further used in test and validate task T3.4 in Spanish laboratory and more broadly with real life events in WP5 - where the demonstration will take place in the 4 pilots mentioned above.

Lastly, there exist administrative connections inside WP4. T4.2 and T4.3 focus on push towards usage of shared data approach. Such a commitment is required as quality data exchanged among partners can be the first step towards recognition of existing constrains in the grid. Furthermore, transparent and fast data exchange is a precondition for grid transition to meet new requirements [12]. Lastly, task 4.4 is dedicated towards ensuring that our developed solutions are a viable for European space. The measure of eligibility will be calculated via Triple Layered Business Model Canvas (TLBMC), where a business case is generated around each developed solution and then inspected through the lens of its societal, environmental and economic impacts. The estimated values are based on a detailed assessment of the individual value propositions of all stakeholders involved.

1.4 Structure of deliverable

Chapter 1 will concisely present the overall objectives of InterSTORE project, followed by goals of WP4 and lastly the dedication of T4.1. Similarly, this chapter will also include relations of WP4 and T4.1 to other work carried in this project. As deliverable D4.1 focuses on new generation energy management systems, the following five chapters will be dedicated

to the presentation of each one. Starting with Flexibility Management Platform whose development will be detailed in chapter 2, followed by Hybrid Distributed Energy Management System with some interesting tests results for the developed interoperable toolkit described in chapter 3. The Home Energy Management System is presented in chapter 4 and the Multi-physics Energy Management System in chapter 5. Finally EV hybrid distributed Energy Management System in chapter 6. Conclusions are gathered in chapter 7.

2 Flexibility Management Platform

As a company, CyberGrid has more than a decade of experience connecting to different assets and information and communication technology (ICT) platforms via various protocols, keeping in mind many of their variations as well. As a result, CyberGrid understands well the struggles related to bridging protocol differences and the shortcomings of each. CyberGrid recognized IEEE2030.5 over NATS as a promising solution with its many possible communication variations, distributed message broker, and range of applications in DER systems. CyberGrid integrated the client-server library directly into its Flexibility Management Platform - CyberNoc. As an additional challenge, CyberGrid decided to start exploring energy communities as potential sources of flexibility. To this end, an energy community toolkit, hybridization tools, and market arbitrage tool adaptation are going to be developed and implemented. All combined will be showcased in two use cases that CyberGrid leads: UC1 - DES Flexibility Market Monetisation, which focuses on enabling monetization of Distributed Energy Resource (DER) flexibility at various markets, and UC2 - Energy community DES utilization, which is all about enhancing community self-sufficiency mode to minimize their reliance on the grid and in turn help the overburdened grid and energy community members to reduce costs.

2.1 Interoperability toolkit

The Client-Server library was developed in T2.1 [7] and represents the starting point for achieving interoperability, which the IEEE2030.5 over NATS offers. Based on this library, CyberGrid upgraded its CyberNoc platform and set up dedicated NATS.

2.1.1 Development steps

Table 1 presents the steps that were taken to reach the objective of natively communicating via IEEE2030.5 over NATS.

Number	Step	Description	Constraints
1.	Inspect the open-source library on GitHub.	Based on the newly developed protocol, the specific attributes were inspected.	Limited knowledge of IEEE2030.5 protocol.
2.	Create a mapping towards the inner system.	As CyberNoc uses RabbitMQ, the internal mapping was created.	No literature to take as a reference.
3.	Creating GW.	Based on the mappings and rules set up, we generate software that will do the conversion automatically.	
4.	Adding a gateway in CyberNoc.	The installation was completed and integrated into the EMS.	
5.	Testing message conversion.	The message from RabbitMQ to IEEE2030.5 is properly translated.	
6.	Testing compliance with IEEE2030.5 standards.	The format of the message equals the required standard, passing the testing procedure.	

7.	Technical connection with assets in the pilot.	The exchange of messages is successful.	
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Table 1 CyberGrid's stepwise plan towards interoperability.

Step 1. required the detailed inspection of a novel protocol of IEEE2030.5 specifications [5]. Thorough inspections gave CyberGrid the insight into differences in InterSTORE's approach from CyberNoc current approach. This task is central for all future steps so considerable time was dedicated to understanding of mapping procedures of IEEE2030.5. The limiting factor in this case was CyberGrid's limited knowledge about the IEEE2030.5 protocol. Note: CyberGrid inspected 2018 variant of the protocol.

Step 2. creates as an output a rulebook for mapping IEEE2030.5 messages to the internal protocol used by CyberNoc, which is RabbitMQ. Here, the various use cases that are supported by NATS were analysed and mapped one by one. For instance, mapping rules when there are two streams active (with the same time resolution) or rules about two simultaneous communications – one to an asset and the other to another EMS.

Step 3. focused on saving the defined rules from the previous step in a programming language as a library. From a library, a dedicated software called gateway (GW) was created, which automatically applies the needed rules and transformation. GW is the centrepiece of CyberNoc's approach towards interoperability.

Step 4. implemented the GW into CyberNoc and opened the connection outwards: this means that assets and EMSs can find the system and request to connect to it. In this step, CyberGrid also deployed a NATS server through which communication travels. For the security of the data, which CyberGrid will collect from the residential pilot NATS server was deployed locally (in AWS cloud) therefore limiting number of possible connections to a selected number defined beforehand.

Step 5. tested the compatibility of messages by comparing the translated messages returned by GW to the expected ones. This testing was done for multiple messages in both directions. At the end of testing, the correct translation was confirmed.

Step 6. inspects if the IEEE2030.5 messages sent out by CyberNoc are in accordance with the official standard. This was confirmed, and with that, CyberGrid can speak IEEE2030.5 (over NATS) natively!

Step 7. is all about showcasing that this technical development work in a real-world environment. CyberGrid will demonstrate this in an Austrian residential pilot project.

2.1.2 Time plan of development

The development steps were done by the technical team at CyberGrid starting in May of 2024 (after the first versions of the client/server were released in the project) and finishing in October 2024. The time plan presented on Figure 3 shows a detailed chronogram.

Figure 3 Time plan of client/server integration in CyberNoc.

Finally, the flexibility management platform is able to connect to assets in the testing laboratory and residential pilot via the new protocol. Figure 4 shows the list of connected devices, where the red rectangle highlights the protocol used for communication.

Figure 4 Connections towards DER in Austrian pilot.

2.2 Connecting to the open data space

Sharing aggregated data is a novelty for CyberGrid as it previously had a limited number of use cases that required such an approach. This was partly because sharing data is generally considered a security risk. That said, the new approach presented by open data spaces offers a trustworthy solution and has been accepted as appropriate by CyberGrid for energy communities. In essence, CyberNoc will aggregate the flexibility for the next day for the energy community members participating in the project.

2.2.1 Development steps

By default, CyberNoc Flexibility management platform aggregates data/energy from various portfolios with different sources of energy (PV, batteries, combined heat and power (CHP), hydro power plants (HPP), etc.) and puts it on balancing markets. For the particular use case of sharing data via the open data space, CyberGrid will aggregate the remaining energy (after

the self-optimisation from the energy community toolkit) and present it as a DSO balancing offer. Table 2 presents the steps taken for the development.

Number	Step	Description	Metric
1.	Integrate the connector in CyberNoc.	Install the connector inside CyberNoc.	Working software.
2.	Connect to open data spaces.	Enable CyberNoc connection to open data spaces via the internet.	Push and pull data from another participant enabled.
3.	Create additional services in the connector and exchange the data.	Contribute to the offered services by adding a CyberNoc use case.	Share the aggregated data in the open data space.

Table 2 CyberGrid's steps toward connection over open data spaces.

Step 1 was the initial step towards sharing the data. As the CyberNoc aggregates data by default, including a connector inside the existing infrastructure was the simplest and cleanest solution for sharing the data. In addition, this way, the security of members' data was not exposed to any additional risk.

Step 2 enabled the connector inside CyberNoc to connect outwards. This step was done with delicacy in order to keep the security as high as possible. For instance, the shared data was anonymised (on the energy community level), meaning that only a combined balancing offer was shared with dedicated partners subscribing to the service.

Step 3 was dedicated to formulating the shared data through a connector as an additional service that could be subscribed to by the DSO or other relevant parties.

2.2.2 Time plan of development

The described steps were done between March and November 2024. Figure 5 show the detailed chronogram of activities.

Figure 5 Time plan of client/server integration in CyberNoc.

The approach is well in use, as can be seen from the list of offered services from the connector. Figure 6 shows the screenshot of the connector, in which the CyberGrid-specific service can be seen.

Figure 6 Offered service from the energy community and CyberGrid.

2.3 Hybridisation tools (deviation fighter, ramping, SoC)

CyberNoc has been working with batteries for the majority of its operational history. That being said, the possibilities that HESS brings to the table require the development of novel operational approaches. To maximize HESS benefits, CyberGrid decided to develop a trio of tools. They are:

- State of Charge (SoC) manager – a tool looking after battery health by managing the window of operational state of charge.
- Deviation fighter – a tool to manage fluctuations of output energy with a PID algorithm.
- Ramping manager – a tool for optimal reach of the required setpoint.

2.3.1 Development steps

The developments are separate from each other, but as they refer to the same segment, they were done in parallel. The steps are presented together in Table 3.

Number	Tool	Step	Description
1.1.	SoC manager	Read the state of charge (SoC) level of the battery asset.	Upon connection to the asset CyberNoc regularly fetches information about the SoC level.
1.2.	SoC manager	Develop a control panel for users of CyberNoc to set up borders.	Set up an interface that saves the parameters of how the battery should be used in specific areas of the SoC.
1.3.	SoC manager	Use the battery according to the defined principles.	Limit/Boost battery charge/discharge based on the defined rules.
2.1.	Deviation fighter	Set up the approach of monitoring deviation.	Present the current output next to the expected one.
2.2.	Deviation fighter	Implement the PID algorithm to nullify the output deviation.	The PID algorithm successfully diminishes existing deviations.
3.1.	Ramping manager	Store ramp requirements.	In CyberNoc, set up a dedicated page that can store different ramping options

			based on market requirements and asset capabilities.
3.2.	Ramping manager	CyberNoc automatically chooses the proper ramping option.	When the system receives activation, it ramps based on the market needs and asset capabilities.

Table 3 steps of development for hybridisation tools.

Step 1.1. revolved around the proper translation of the battery SoC attributes and their presentation in CyberNoc. This step was additionally challenging due to the fact that different battery manufacturers might use different sets of output signals. Having this in mind, the CyberNoc feature is developed with an approach that allows changing of SoC reading attributes for proper translation into CyberNoc.

Step 1.2 focused on setting up a rule plan in CyberNoc that a user can define and put into motion through the User Interface (UI). The main idea is to set up borders within which a battery can be freely operated and marketed. This is set for the whole battery and for each market in which the battery is participating. In case the SoC state exceeds this range, a counter bid is put on the dedicated Intraday market, which results in active SoC management. On Figure 7 you can see an example of this tool's UI.

Step 1.3. focused on using the developed approaches in battery operation. This included testing of the developed system and monitoring its performance.

Figure 7 Presentation of SoC management UI in CyberNoc.

Step 2.1. connects the required output by individual market to the actual output that the system provides. In this manner, we can compare the two and visualize the deviation. As any major deviation results in penalties for CyberNoc operators, CyberGrid developed mitigation techniques. Moreover, as the comparison is ongoing continuously during provision on the market, the two outputs are compared in the backend of CyberNoc automatically.

Step 2.2. builds on the above visualisation of deviation by developing an automated approach for recognising the deviation and taking measures to nullify/minimize them. The solution implemented is a PID controller [13], which corrects any deviations by combining the effects of its three components: proportional, integral, and derivative (hence the name PID).

$$PID(t) = Pn(t) + In(t) + Dn(t)$$

Each component presents a different approach to tackling deviation:

Proportional component Pn presents the change of output as a proportion of the deviation.

$$Pn(t) = kp * deviation(t) = kp * abs(actualoutput(t) - expectedoutput(t))$$

- The integral component In is generated as an integral of the output error over time. For example, if there is an error after the application of proportional control, the integral term seeks to eliminate the residual error by adding a control effect due to the historic cumulative value of the error [13]. When the error is eliminated, the integral term will cease to grow.

$$In(t) = ki * \int_0^t deviation(x) * dx$$

- Differential component Dn is an estimate of the future trend of deviation, based on its current rate of change. This component is described as anticipatory control, as it is seeking to reduce the effect of the error by exerting a control influence generated by the rate of error change [13]. We calculate it as

$$Dn(t) = kd * \frac{deviation(t)}{dt}$$

The controller is a feedback-based control loop mechanism [13], which means that its output is compared to the input, and if needed, the process is reiterated. After the successful development of the PID controller, it was then put in use on different markets on which Cyber-Grid participates with various assets. Schematics of the PID controller implemented in CyberNoc are shown on Figure 8.

Figure 8 Schematics of the PID controller logic integrated in CyberNoc.

Step 3.1. focuses on storing ramping rules for different markets (speed of ramp, allowed deviation, time frame) and assets that provide the energy (maximum and minimum ramp possible, reserved capacity for internal needs) and connects them based on which markets the assets are participating in.

Step 3.2. builds upon the defined ramp specifications by imposing needed rules on how an asset should be activated. This development considers asset capabilities and limitations and activates them accordingly. The ramp presented is also in line with market requirements and deviation margins.

2.3.2 Time plan of development

As mentioned before, the developed methods were worked on in parallel. That is why the time plan on Figure 9 is dynamic.

Figure 9 Time plan of the hybridization approaches in CyberNoc.

2.4 Market Arbitrage tool adaptation

All envisioned profits from the energy communities' assets are based on offering available energy on different energy or balancing markets. To enable such novel revenue streams for the energy community, connections to multiple markets were developed in addition to the arbitrage tool, which compares prices on individual markets and bids energy on the optimal one. Altogether, this approach provides maximisation of market revenues for the energy community. As the amount of available energy is small, the benefits of the arbitrage tool will be shown through simulation. Moreover, the targeted markets are the Intraday and manual Frequency Restoration Reserve (mFRR) energy market.

2.4.1 Development steps

The development of the market arbitrage tool was done in close coordination with the open data spaces and energy community toolkit. Close coordination with the first, relates to the fact that all remaining energy, not sold on markets, will be packaged and sent as DSO offers over open data spaces. The coordination with the energy community toolkit is more obvious, as its output is the remaining energy, which can be marketed. Taken development steps are again presented in Table 4.

Number	Step	Description	Measure
1.	Connect to energy markets.	CyberNoc connects to mFRR energy market and the Intraday market.	Ongoing communications to markets.
2.	Calculate available energy	Receive the amount of remaining energy after self-consumption	For each 15-minute block, the amount of available energy in MWh is listed.
3.	Forecast and compare market prices	Gather historic market prices, forecast the prices for the current day, and present the optimal.	The system sends bids of available energy for the upcoming day to the best market.
4.	Bid on the best market	Install the connector inside the CyberNoc platform.	
5.	Calculate additional revenues	The system will showcase the benefits presented by marketing the energy compared to no market participation.	increase in revenue due to market participation.

Table 4 development steps for the market arbitrage tools.

Step 1. creates the basis on which market participation is based, as we will technically connect to targeted markets. In our case, the viable markets are the Intraday energy market (rolling energy auction) and the mFRR energy market. Due to limitations of assets and a limited window in which we can market assets (as we need them to be ready for the needs of households), we will not enter capacity markets, as their product duration is much longer (4h in Austria).

Step 2. connects participation on the market with available energy. For this to work, market arbitrage will be connected to the energy community toolkit, which will manage the generated and reserved energy for the needs of self-consumption. The energy community will forecast available remaining energy for the next day and send it to the market arbitrage tool.

Step 3. is the crucial part of the process as we develop an approach by which the system chooses the best market to participate in. Comparing balancing market (mFRR energy) to wholesale market (Intraday) can prove tricky, as comparing the prices alone might not give you the full picture. To make the comparison more appropriate, we included in the decision process the forecasted probability of activation. Combining the two, we estimate revenues and decide based on this measure.

Step 4. places bids on the optimal market and waits for the results. As the amount of energy is too small to participate in the markets this part will be simulated based on actual market results.

Step 5. considers the results of the market (simulation) results, generates possible revenues, and compares them to alternatives (no market participation, DSO bids).

The UI presentation of the best bidding strategy, and its results, can be observed on Figure 10.

Figure 10 Presentation of the market arbitrage tool in CyberNoc.

2.4.2 Time plan of development

CyberGrid allocated resources to adapt the Market arbitrage tool between February 2024 and March 2025. The adaptation timeline is presented on Figure 11.

Figure 11 Time plan of the market arbitrage tool development in CyberNoc.

2.5 Energy Community toolkit

The focus point of the EMS development for CyberGrid is to create a tool that optimizes the energy produced by energy communities. This is of most importance as it is the first, and sometimes the only, benefit energy community members get from participating in this project. The overall goal is to better use batteries in storing and discharging energy, based on weather forecasts and the needs of community members. The high-level presentation of the Energy Community toolkit workflow can be analysed on Figure 12.

Figure 12 Presentation of actions and steps in the energy community toolkit.

2.5.1 Development steps

Table 5 describes the new functionality and how each development step was conducted.

Number	Step	Description	Measure
1.	Automatic adding of assets.	When a new device is connected to CyberNoc, the device is self-created in the system.	Attributes are generated.
2.	Forecast generation for the next day.	Receive irradiation from a third party and calculate the expected energy generation for the next day.	Irradiation is imported, and the generation for the next day is forecasted.
3.	Maximisation of energy.	Based on the forecast, the optimal behaviour of each asset type is set.	Increased self-sufficiency.
4.	Connect to the market arbitrage tool.	Coordinate targeted self-sufficiency with market participation.	shown increased revenues/benefits by entering markets.
5.	Send activation/reservation commands.	Based on schedules and sold energy, send command signals to devices.	Received commands from devices.

Table 5 Development steps for the energy community toolkit.

Step 1. defined by the new protocol IEEE2030.5 and its presentation in CyberNoc (via developed GW) revolves around providing the automatic registration of new assets and their attributes in CyberNoc. This step has a huge significance due to the fact that energy communities have many assets of various types and producers.

Step 2. builds upon automatically added assets by using the gathered data, and using it to understand their behaviour. Later, this is extended to include forecasting of production (of PVs) based on the irradiation forecast for the next day.

Step 3. revolves around the forecast of production. In essence, three modes were developed: high production, low production, and normal mode. If the forecast shows huge production for the next day, a less conservative approach is chosen for batteries. This means that their energy is used fully for the needs of households in the morning, and they are not charged from PVs. This is because there is a big probability that PV production will stay high throughout the day and in times of low household consumption battery will get charged. Alternatively, if the predicted production is low, the battery is charged the night before, as the prices are low and the costs are reduced. This makes sense as the alternative would be to take energy from the grid, which is much more expensive at that time. If the forecast does not show high enough production to activate the first approach, but also not low enough for the second battery, and energy community assets remain in normal/default mode.

Step 4. adds to the previous step by connecting to the market that is necessary as optimisation in a low production environment can be achieved only if CyberNoc can charge energy community batteries from the grid. In our use case, we focus on charging from the Intraday market. In high production times, the abundance of energy can also be bundled together and placed as a bid on the mFRR energy market or Intraday. This is unlikely to happen due to a limited number of assets.

Step 5. is sending activation/reservation commands to the batteries and other assets based on the created plan. This is a challenging task as we have plenty of different assets with different protocols used.

2.5.2 Time plan of development

Work on the Energy Community toolkit is presented in Figure 13 and was done from February 2024 until February 2025.

Figure 13 Time plan of the Energy Community toolkit integration in CyberNoc.

3 Hybrid Distributed Energy Management System

The Hybrid Distributed Energy Management System (HyDEMS) is an advanced energy management solution designed by HESStec company to optimize the operation of hybrid energy storage systems (HESS) and distributed energy resources (DERs). HyDEMS enhances grid stability, ensures efficient resource utilization, and improves system operation by covering a wide range of services from high-power fast services to high-energy services. One of its key features of such an energy management system is the Interoperability Toolkit, which facilitates seamless communication, integration, and control of diverse energy assets.

3.1 Interoperability toolkit

The Interoperability Toolkit within the HyDEMS, enables robust interaction between various energy components, legacy systems, and modern smart grid protocols. It ensures compliance with the IEEE2030.5 standard while incorporating legacy protocol converters for enhanced interoperability. The toolkit consists of multiple functional modules, including the Communication Interface Deployment, Hybridization Tool, and State of Function (SOF) Tool. To fulfil the task of the work package, some of the main activities are summarized as follows:

The activities begin with Communication Architecture Development (LPC) to establish the core framework (Apr–Aug 2024), followed by Hybridization Tool Updates and Tests to refine integration tools (Jun–Nov 2024). Concurrently, SoF Development and Simulation designs and models the system (Apr–Jun 2024), leading to SoF Implementation and Translation for real-world deployment (Nov 2024–Feb 2025). The process culminates with Showcase and Full Test Services for validation and demonstrations (Jan–Mar 2025), supported throughout by Cloud Monitoring Updates and Data Analysis, and Reporting for optimization and insights. Figure 14 presents the time plan of the developments HESStec did.

Figure 14 Time plan of the HyDEMS development, considering its interoperability toolkit.

3.1.1 Communication interface deployment

Effective communication is fundamental to achieving a fully integrated energy management system. The Communication Interface Deployment module ensures that HyDEMS can interact seamlessly with different control architectures, including SCADA, IEC standard, and Modbus-based systems. Key features include:

- Legacy Protocol Converter: Allows compatibility with older energy management and monitoring systems.
- IEEE2030.5 Compliance: Ensures seamless interaction with modern smart grid infrastructures.
- Secure Data Exchange: Implements encryption and authentication mechanisms to protect grid communication.
- Real-time Monitoring & Control: Provides a low-latency interface for decision-making in hybrid energy storage and distributed energy systems.

Error! Reference source not found., as an example of communication and real-time monitoring test, shows the graphical interface of the PCS4 grid following converter for managing the event by changing the parameter setpoints as one of its inputs.

Figure 15 DERs interface used for UC7 in GridLab.

3.1.2 Hybridization tool

The Hybridization Tool within HyDEMS is designed to optimize the performance of hybrid energy storage systems (HESS) by dynamically managing multiple storage technologies. This tool enhances the efficiency of energy storage integration by:

- Coordinating and hybridizing different storage system technologies, facilitating different operating modes of conversion systems, such as Grid-Forming and Grid-Following conversion systems.
- Optimizing Power Dispatch: ensures efficient distribution of power between batteries, supercapacitors, and other storage elements.
- Dynamic Resource Allocation: uses predictive algorithms to allocate energy based on demand, grid frequency, and market signals.

- Interoperability with DERs: supports flexible integration with different DERS such as renewables, GFM converter, and GFL converter system, and other generation sources.

As explained during our activities in WP1 (D1.2, D1.4) [7], there is not a single technology that covers both power and energy services in a cost-effective way, so the traditional BESS approach often leads to non-optimal or even to unprofitable solutions. Thus, the role and the necessity of a hybrid approach and hybridization algorithm, which can mix different technologies, will be important, especially for future grid scenarios, while various services are demanded by system operators.

Hybrid storage technology is a mix of different sources of energy storage technologies for providing a wide range of solutions, from power-based storage components to energy-based storage systems, covering the whole spectrum of possible hybrid power/energy ratios.

An example of the used hybridization tool is shown in Figure 16 showing a one level hybridization concept where from the power profile reference that the HESS has to provide, the total response is divided by different distributed HESS system, (for example the energy/power battery and the UCAP/power battery or different combination), that is a combination of two basic kind of technology: energy battery, power battery or UCAP for covering wide range of services. As shown in this figure, the power reference is divided into two signals, a low-frequency signal and a high-frequency signal. In this way, the energy/power battery will oversee providing the low-frequency signal, and the UCAP/power battery will be in charge of providing the high-frequency signal.

Figure 16: One level hybridization scheme.

3.1.3 State of Function (SoF) tool development

It is crucial to recognize that distributed and hybrid energy storage resources, such as UCAPS, home batteries, EV charging stations, and other energy storage technologies, are becoming increasingly prevalent in modern grid systems. However, the diversity of technologies and manufacturers poses challenges in comparing and assessing their performance. This is where the System-of-Functions (SoF) framework serves as an advanced interoperability tool. SoF offers a standardized method for describing and evaluating energy storage systems, irrespective of their technology or manufacturer, by breaking them down into functional components like power conversion, energy storage, and control systems, and establishing a common language to define their capabilities.

The figure of merit called State of Function (SoF) has been conceived for the implementation of virtualization, in order to simplify the optimization process and the interoperability with end-users, external systems, and energy or power management systems (EMS or PMS).

The State of Function (SoF) is a dimensionless vector that quantifies the availability of one or more storage devices for service operation or grid functionalities, such as time shifting, primary frequency regulation, or virtual inertia. The Figure 17 shows a system where the hybridization of different technologies can be found.

Figure 17 Generic scheme of hybridization of different technologies.

As an example shown on Figure 18, it can be three different technologies for hybridization:

- Technology 1: ion-lithium battery with high power density ($j = 1$)
- Technology 2: ion-lithium battery with high energy density ($j = 2$)
- Technology 3: ultracapacitors ($j = 3$)

The services that will provide these technologies are:

- Service 1: time shifting and energy arbitrage ($i = 1$)
- Service 2: renewable resources following ($i = 2$)
- Service 3: primary frequency regulation ($i = 3$)
- Service 4: virtual inertia ($i = 4$)

Figure 18 Scheme example of three different technologies.

Implementing a State of Function (SoF) monitoring system for a HESS system can involve several steps:

1. Identify the relevant system variables: Determine the key parameters that need to be monitored and analysed to calculate the SoF. This can include variables such as the energy of each DES component, the state of charge (SoC), the state of health (SoH), temperature, voltage, current, maximum/minimum allowed power, and inject/absorb condition modes for each of the storage components.
2. Develop a monitoring system: Install sensors and data acquisition systems to monitor the relevant system variables in real-time. The sensors can be wired or wireless, depending on the specific application. The data acquisition system can be a dedicated system or a software-based solution that collects data from the sensors and processes it.
3. Develop a SoF calculation algorithm: Develop an algorithm that calculates the SoF based on the monitored system variables. The algorithm can be simple or complex, depending on the specific application. The algorithm should consider the performance characteristics of each storage component and be able to make decisions on how to allocate and balance the service/load between the different DERs. The SoF algorithm defines the different modes of operation for the hybrid energy storage system based on the SoC and temperature of each storage technology.
4. Integrate the SoF monitoring system with the hybrid energy storage system: Integrate the monitoring system with the control system of the hybrid energy storage system so that the SoF can be used to make real-time decisions on the operation of the system.
5. Test and validate the system: Test the SoF monitoring system in real-world conditions and validate its performance. This can involve testing the system under different operating conditions and comparing the results to expected performance metrics.

3.1.3.1 Developed Input and output of SoF

To calculate the State of Function, it is necessary to introduce several inputs. Graphically, the Figure 19 shows each input and output.

Figure 19 Inputs/Outputs SoF function.

The algorithm inputs are obtained from measurements or communications and, for each technology, comprise:

- State of Health (SoH): the maximum level of charge of a battery relative to its initial value when it is first used.

$$SOH = [SOH_1 \quad \cdots \quad SOH_j]$$

- State of Charge (SoC): the remaining capacity available in the storage system at a given time.

$$SOC = [SOC_1 \quad \cdots \quad SOC_j]$$

- Maximum discharge current (i_{max_dis}): maximum current injected by each technology.

$$max_{dis} = [i_{max,dis,1} \quad \cdots \quad i_{max,dis,j}]$$

- Maximum charge current (i_{max_ch}): maximum current absorbed by the storage system.

$$max_{ch} = [i_{max,ch,1} \quad \cdots \quad i_{max,ch,j}]$$

- Instantaneous power (iP): power injected or absorbed by each technology.

$$iP = [iP_1 \quad \cdots \quad iP_j]$$

- Faults/Alarms (F): in case of any technology is unavailable due to a fault or maintenance.

$$F = [F_1 \quad \cdots \quad F_j]$$

On the other hand, the output of this algorithm is obtained as follows:

- Availability matrix (M): In this matrix can be found the weight of each parameter in relation to the functionality.
- Corrected availability matrix (M_c): This matrix considers the weight matrix per functionality and technology.
- State of Function (SoF): Dimensionless vector that quantifies the capacity of each system in relation to functionality.

In summary, the function can be written as:

$$[M, M_c, SoF] = SoF_{function}(SOH, SOC, max_{dis}, max_{ch}, F, iP)$$

So, for each system with different storage devices hybridized it obtained a SoF vector.

As shown in Figure 20, in a low hierarchy control layer, each storage technology or asset has its own SoF. Following a hierarchical or distributed approach, the EMS/PMS creates a single SoF of the hybrid storage solution or a microgrid. Different approaches can be used for adapting the SoF to the real system application:

- Hierarchical or vertical approach: Simplifies the processing and facilitates the operation by higher control layers, decoupling low-level issues from the top-level operations, allowing a lighter implementation of real-time and optimisation algorithms. This hierarchical approach allows having multiple levels of virtualization. In case of a non-autonomous approach, EMS/PMS guides end-users in case of external operation, indicating the possible services (and combination of them) to be provided.

- Distributed or horizontal approach: In the case of coordinated operations with other control or energy management devices of other systems, the SoF is the base of the exchange of information, facilitating the coordination and integration of distributed storage systems with multiple technologies, energy vectors and loads as a single entity such as a Virtual Storage Plants.

Figure 20 SoF dimensionless vector for each system.

The following lines show an example of the SoF function. The system that is used for the example is based on the scheme in Figure 17 and consists of UCAPs, high power density BESS, and high energy density BESS connected in AC. Four services are evaluated in this example: virtual inertia, primary frequency regulation, renewable resource following, and time shifting.

As explained earlier, the inputs are SoH, SoC, $imax_{dis}$, $imax_{ch}$, iP and F . For a moment, these variables can take the following values for each technology:

$$\begin{aligned}
 SOH &= [0.9 \quad 0.9 \quad 0.9]pu \\
 SOC &= [0.6 \quad 0.6 \quad 0.6]pu \\
 max_{dis} &= [100 \quad 200 \quad 2600]A \\
 max_{ch} &= [100 \quad 200 \quad 2600]A \\
 iP &= [0 \quad 0 \quad 0]MW \\
 F &= [0 \quad 0 \quad 0]
 \end{aligned}$$

The outputs obtained from the SoF function are:

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} 0.9422 & 0.7006 & 0.8130 \\ 0.6703 & 0.6525 & 0.7030 \\ 0.6059 & 0.6372 & 0.7158 \\ 0.5681 & 0.6271 & 0.7219 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$M_c = \begin{bmatrix} 0.9422 & 0.3503 & 0 \\ 0.6033 & 0.5872 & 0 \\ 0.0606 & 0.5735 & 0.1432 \\ 0 & 0.0627 & 0.7219 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$SoF = \begin{bmatrix} 0.8617 \\ 0.6614 \\ 0.6477 \\ 0.7133 \end{bmatrix}$$

If, instead of using inputs for a moment, real measurements are used, a plot on Figure 21 it can be obtained, which shows the SoF along 16 h of simulation.

Figure 21 Example of the developed SoF calculation for 16 h.

3.2 Service provision of the EMS in different modes

In this section, the idea is to test the functionality and present several showcases of the developed HyDEMS testing hybridization, DERs functionalities, and SoF capabilities during different tests. As explained in WP1, the schematic of UC7 developed in Gridlab in Valencia is presented in Figure 22.

Figure 22 Schematic of the developed scenario of UC7 in Gridlab Valencia.

As shown in this figure, the developed HyDEMS is based on a single LPC for bidirectional communication between a grid-forming (GFM) power converter called DER1, as well as DER2 during events, and an EMS, the aggregator. This approach ensures seamless data exchange while adhering to the IEEE 2030.5 standard, enabling real-time monitoring and control of grid-forming DER1 HESS converters. The LPC acts as a protocol translator, converting the proprietary Modbus protocol used by the power inverter into the standardized IEEE 2030.5 protocol required by the EMS, and vice versa. The LPC was deployed on a Docker, reachable from the local network, to receive and send power setpoints from the DER1 and DER2 to EMS as a bidirectional approach, whose log file example is shown in Figure 23 below:

```

lpclog
12 2025-03-26 15:17:05,107 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.modbus.AbstractModbusRequestHandler -- Sending Modbus request to device: 1 {}
13 2025-03-26 15:17:05,156 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ModbusHandler -- Bytes: [0, 0] {}
14 2025-03-26 15:17:05,156 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ModbusHandler -- Registers: [0] {}
15 2025-03-26 15:17:05,192 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- path: 1532, value: 0 {}
16 2025-03-26 15:17:05,221 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Transformed message: {
17   "DER": {
18     "description": "Gridlab Converter",
19     "mrid": {
20       "value": "1"
21     },
22     "activePower": {
23       "multiplier": {
24         "value": "1"
25       },
26       "value": 0
27     },
28     "lastUpdateTime": 1743002225157
29   }
30 } {}
31 2025-03-26 15:17:05,221 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Publishing message to topic: event/send with message: {
32   "DER": {
33     "description": "Gridlab Converter",
34     "mrid": {
35       "value": "1"
36     },
37     "activePower": {
38       "multiplier": {
39         "value": "1"
40       },
41       "value": 0
42     },
43     "lastUpdateTime": 1743002225157
44   }
45 } {}
46 2025-03-26 15:17:05,221 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.nats.AbstractNatsRequestHandler -- Publishing message: {
47   "DER": {
48     "description": "Gridlab Converter",
49     "mrid": {
50       "value": "1"
51     },
52     "activePower": {

```

Figure 23 The log files from the implemented HyDEMS with LPC in GridLab Spain pilot.

The log files from the LPC were stored from the demonstration time window, as well as the necessary raw data in Excel format for KPI purposes, and will be shared within the project.

3.2.1 Auto synchronization and grid forming (GFM DER1) test

The purpose of this test is to verify that the GFM DER1 is capable of forming the grid and of quickly resynchronizing itself in the event of an island network reconnection to the mainland after synchronization. In this test, a full synchronization is tested from the island to the grid-connected modes. For doing this test, converter DEAR1 of the UC7 is worked and tested in different modes, such as an island situation and then switch to grid connected mode for activation of other functionalities such as synchronization control. For doing this test a simplified schematic of the performed scenario is shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24 DER1 GridLab scenario for synchronization test.

The initial SoC of the UCAP was set to 70%, and the HESS system is stated that after getting synchronized with the main breaker, called HUT, will be closed, and the HESS system will work in grid-connected mode. This action will be important to check, since later in the voltage dip test it will be used.

In Figure 25 the results of the full test with all the captured signals are presented. As shown in this figure, first the converter starts in island mode, and after that it switches to uGrid, making the synchronizer active. The moment of synchronizer activation can be observed with one small spike in island frequency (brown curve), and it makes the error of synchronization zero (synchronization error is shown by blue curve). Then the main breaker is closed, and the converter works in grid-connected mode, showing some small dynamic variation in active and reactive current signals due to interactions with the main grid.

Figure 25 Full DER1 synchronization test: synchronizer OFF in island, then Synchronizer is ON, switched to the grid-connected mode after synchronization.

3.2.2 Grid following (GFL - DER2 FS4G)

The objective of this test is to evaluate the performance of the grid-following converters defined in Use Case UC7. As illustrated in Figure 22, two of the grid-following converter stations, namely PCS3 and PCS4, are configured to emulate a weak grid and a renewable energy source, respectively.

In this scenario, PCS4 is designed to replicate the behavior of a low-inertia weak grid, while PCS3 is controlled to operate as a variable renewable energy source, such as a photovoltaic (PV) system.

To assess the functionality of the System of Functions (SoF), two test scenarios are implemented: a virtual inertia test and a power firming test.

- In the first one, PCS4 operates as a weak grid. An under-frequency event (shown in Figure 26) is intentionally introduced to evaluate the response of the developed HyDEMS (Hybrid Dynamic Energy Management System). The goal is to analyze the system's capability to support frequency stability through inertia emulation.
- Following the virtual inertia test, a firming test is conducted using PCS3. In this test, as shown in Figure 27, a realistic PV generation profile is applied to PCS3 to emulate typical fluctuations in solar power output. The system's ability to smooth out this variability is assessed, as illustrated in the corresponding figure.

These coordinated tests provide insights into how the hybrid system responds under dynamic grid conditions and variable renewable inputs, demonstrating its capacity to deliver grid support services effectively.

Figure 26 Power profile generated by PSC4.

Figure 27 Power profile generated by PSC3 for firming test.

3.2.3 Firming and frequency service with renewable profile

To validate the functionality of the developed HyDEMS (Hybrid Distributed Energy Management System) with its latest control features aligned with IEEE 2030.5 and Local Power Coordinator (LPC), a series of tests were conducted. These tests evaluate the virtual inertia (VI) frequency response and firming capabilities provided by a grid-following (GFL) distributed energy source (DER2) in a lab environment. Simultaneously, the response of the Hybrid Energy Storage System (HESS), equipped with an advanced grid-forming (GFM) DER1 controller integrating ultracapacitors (UCAP) and batteries, was analysed and demonstrated. The results highlight the successful interoperability of the State of Function (SoF) algorithm and the effective hybridization of storage technologies, where HyDEMS dynamically coordinates DERs based on real-time storage status.

The capture of DER1 converter equipped with HESS is presented by its provided interface in Figure 28 and Figure 29.

Figure 28 illustrates the active power injection as well as important signals from the HESS DER1 during a virtual inertia (VI) event, where the ultracapacitor (UCAP) rapidly responds to frequency deviations. The fast power delivery demonstrates UCAP's dominance in high-speed services, while the State of Function (SoF) remains high (close to 1), confirming its suitability for fast grid support.

Figure 28 Power Real-time interface of the HESS DER1 system response during VI event.

In Figure 29, the capture is related to a firming event after the VI test. In this part of the test battery plays a primary role in power firming, providing sustained energy output compared to the UCAP. The hybridization strategy ensures optimal resource allocation, with the battery's SoF being higher for firming services, while the UCAP contributes minimally in this scenario.

Figure 29 Power Real time interface of the HESS DER1 system response during firming event.

Additional analysis has been done using the raw data imported as an Excel file. As shown in Figure 30, the combined current contribution of the battery (BESS) and ultracapacitor

(UCAP) under different grid services is presented. The UCAP supplies high bursts of current during VI events, whereas the battery delivers steadier current during firming, proving the complementary nature of hybrid storage. This test confirms the operation of hybrid elements within the system.

Figure 30 Current contribution of HESS system in DER1 – Hybridization of BESS and UCAP.

The successful implementation of SoF is also further analyzed within the next plots on Figure 31. The State of Function (SoF) values for both UCAP and battery for different services are displayed, highlighting UCAP's high SoF (close to 1) for fast services (VI) and the battery's higher SoF for firming. This validates the interoperability toolkit's ability to prioritize resources based on service requirements.

Figure 31 SoF values during test events, VI and Firming with LPC.

It is also worth highlighting that, as shown in Figure 32, in addition to the available interfaces, a live visualization of HyDEMS managing both virtual inertia (VI) and firming events has been

enabled within the HESStec laboratory facilities. This demonstration showcases seamless communication between the DERs and the HESS, with the system dynamically adjusting power sharing between the UCAP and the battery, proving effective hybridization and interoperability under real-world conditions.

Figure 32. Real time monitoring demonstration of VI and Firming at HESStec.

4 Home Energy Management System

The Home Energy Management System (HEMS) was upgraded based on a microservice approach in the project, in order to incorporate battery dispatch capabilities, particularly hybrid system dispatch. This was done as a backend development, which ensures the data-sharing of data with CapWatt (PT pilot Site). In addition to the new backend update, a web application was developed for broader use. This was released as open-source and included in the project dedicated GitHub [8].

The data used to show the new features of the HEMS (the Hybrid dispatch) was provided in the context of the Portuguese use case UC05. As inputs, the microservice requires the PV generation on site from the PV arrays on the rooftop of Building 4A, and the load demand forecast of the building. This was important to forecast the remaining load to be supplied by the battery system after self-consumption. Furthermore, in order to run the optimal dispatch function, which minimizes the cost of electricity consumption or minimizes the average emissions expected for the day ahead, these two datasets were also retrieved from well-known or complementary websites, further explained in the upcoming sub-chapters. The output of this service is the combined dispatch of the batteries, considering the expected degradation.

It should be mentioned that, in UC05, the IEEE2030.5 LPC was also used to retrieve a set of variables from the lithium battery inverter. The incorporation of the LPC was done in the dedicated Battery Energy Management System (BEMS) at CapWatt's site. In this sense, since two energy management systems exist (HEMS and the BEMS), the HEMS provided the optimal dispatch of the HESS system, and CapWatt was responsible for providing the settings/commands to the hybrid battery system via the BMS. The existing communication protocol in use was Modbus, hence, this conversion was considered in the configuration files of the LPC. In fact, in order to avoid interrupting the current communication (which is tied to a specific business model to explore the battery functioning), the IEEE2030.5 LPC was deployed redundantly (in parallel), as shown in Figure 33 below.

Figure 33 Connection architecture between the systems.

The LPC was deployed in the local Battery Energy Management System (BEMS) to receive 3 variables from the lithium battery (current, active power, and frequency), whose log file example is shown in the Figure 34 below:

```

2024-12-12 16:31:43,028 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.modbus.AbstractModbusRequestHandler -- Sending Modbus request to device: 1 {}
2024-12-12 16:31:43,053 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ModbusHandler -- Bytes: [0, 16] {}
2024-12-12 16:31:43,054 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ModbusHandler -- Registers: [16] {}
2024-12-12 16:31:43,055 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- path: 27, value: 5001 {}
2024-12-12 16:31:43,056 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- path: 29, value: 0 {}
2024-12-12 16:31:43,056 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- path: 32, value: 16 {}
2024-12-12 16:31:43,057 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Transformed message: {
  "lastUpdateTime": 1734021103054,
  "EventStatus": {
    "Grid frequency": 5001,
    "Output active power": 0,
    "potentiallySuperseded": false
  },
  "interval": {
    "Input 1 current": 16
  }
} {}
2024-12-12 16:31:43,057 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Publishing message to topic: capwatts with message: {
  "lastUpdateTime": 1734021103054,
  "EventStatus": {
    "Grid frequency": 5001,
    "Output active power": 0,
    "potentiallySuperseded": false
  },
  "interval": {
    "Input 1 current": 16
  }
} {}
2024-12-12 16:31:43,058 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.nats.AbstractNatsRequestHandler -- Publishing message: {
  "lastUpdateTime": 1734021103054,
  "EventStatus": {
    "Grid frequency": 5001,
    "Output active power": 0,
    "potentiallySuperseded": false
  },
  "interval": {
    "Input 1 current": 16
  }
}

```

Figure 34 The log files from the LPC in the Portuguese pilot.

The log files from the LPC were stored from the demonstration time window, for KPI purposes, and will be shared within the project.

4.1 Price and emission Incentive retrieval and incorporation

As introduced before, the HEMS requires one of two possible incentives to be minimized. The integration of price and emission incentives into the energy management framework, represents a crucial step towards optimizing hybrid energy storage systems. By leveraging day-ahead market signals and environmental impact data, the system enhances both economic efficiency and sustainability in energy operations. The Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) model used, serves as the foundation for this optimization, allowing for dynamic decision-making based on predefined objectives. The model evaluates hybrid energy storage systems that combine multiple technologies, incorporating key parameters such as tariff signals, which reflect market-driven electricity prices, environmental impact signals based on carbon emission factors, and the initial capital cost of each storage technology, expressed both in financial (€/kWh) and environmental terms (gCO₂/kWh). The prices are acquired using the ENTSO-E API for Portugal, and the emissions are from a federated learning platform called Sentinel [14] powered by InescTEC, which makes use of the Electricity maps' historical data.

Rather than operating as a multi-objective algorithm, the model provides flexibility for users to prioritize either cost minimization or emission minimization, according to their strategic goals. This approach ensures that energy dispatch decisions are optimized based on market conditions, regulatory incentives, and operational constraints. The model relies on two primary input categories: market data, encompassing electricity prices and emissions from the electricity mix, and the building's load consumption, which provides insights into energy demand patterns. By integrating emission coefficients into the optimization process, the system is able to quantify the carbon footprint of energy operations, facilitating more environmentally conscious decision-making.

By incorporating these components, the model ensures that energy operations remain economically taking into account the degradation, of the joint dispatch of the batteries in terms of cost and carbon intensity, of each of the 7 possible types of batteries available in the model.

Figure 35 illustrates the daily market prices and emission changes, considered as inputs, as an example. They are provided with an hourly time step and collected every day to run the model, which is hosted on a server and programmed to run at 19h every day.

Figure 35 Examples of the day-ahead prices (a) and emissions (b) for a given day.

4.2 Forecasting Services adaptation to be applied to CapWatt Building

As mentioned before, in order to program the battery system operation, the load demand of building 4A had to be forecasted. In this regard, a machine-learning-based forecasting algorithm based on the well-known XGBoost was developed specifically for CapWatt's building. This module is an existing microservice from InescTEC's HEMS, and it retrieves the weather forecast variables for the following day. The data is acquired from the Open-Meteo API. Then, with the trained model based on historical consumption and generation data of the local PV provides just before 19h its input to the optimization model. By leveraging these insights, the system is able to generate refined energy demand forecasts, and assign the battery capacity available to discharge into the building. The cycle of the battery is based on a daily dispatch, which means that whatever energy stored, is discharged to the building throughout the day. Hence, the initial and final SoC are the same.

The forecasting module delivered an accuracy of 86% (r2Score), which for the application is quite a high accuracy to consider. The ability to predict future energy consumption with high precision allows for improved resource allocation, reducing unnecessary energy expenditures and ensuring a more balanced and efficient energy supply. The forecasting outputs are subsequently fed into the dispatch optimization process, where they serve as a key input for determining the most efficient operational strategies.

This predictive capability is particularly valuable in the context of hybrid energy storage systems, where the coordination between different storage technologies depends on accurate demand forecasting. By minimizing uncertainty and enhancing decision-making processes, the forecasting module contributes to the overall performance of the Home Energy Management System, reinforcing its ability to deliver cost-effective and sustainable energy solutions.

Figure 36 provides an example of the forecasted load for a given day. It can be seen that the middle part of the plot, coinciding with midday, is when the load is minimum. This is because of the PV generation that has an opposite curve, resulting in auto-consumption at its maximum point around those hours. The remaining part of the load is then, the one that must be supplied by the HESS.

Figure 36 Example of a load forecast generated by the HEMS microservice.

4.3 Load optimization with dispatch recommendation

The optimization of Hybrid Energy Storage Systems (HESS) represents a key strategy for reducing energy supply costs and minimizing environmental impact, while addressing the challenges associated with renewable energy integration. By leveraging advanced optimization techniques, the system ensures an efficient balance between different storage technologies, optimizing both economic and operational performance.

The optimization process is based on a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) approach, which provides precise dispatch recommendations tailored to the characteristics of the available energy storage technologies. These include lithium batteries, vanadium redox flow batteries (VRFB), lead-acid batteries, nickel-cadmium (NiCd) batteries, sodium-sulphur (NaS) batteries, flywheels, and supercapacitors. Each of these technologies presents distinct advantages in terms of efficiency, energy density, degradation rates, and response time. The model strategically coordinates their operation to maximize synergies: while supercapacitors offer high efficiency for rapid energy response, vanadium batteries exhibit lower degradation rates, extending system lifespan and ensuring long-term reliability.

The optimization algorithm operates on a daily basis, incorporating multiple data inputs to refine its dispatch recommendations. It processes battery characteristics, load forecasts, and market incentives, which include both price signals and environmental impact coefficients. By continuously adjusting energy dispatch strategies, the model ensures that HESS operations are aligned with cost minimization or emission reduction objectives, depending on the system’s predefined priorities.

Once the optimization process is complete, the dispatch recommendation is transmitted to a database implemented for data exchange with the pilot. These inputs/setpoints are then provided to the local Battery Energy Management System (BEMS). An example is provided in Figure 37 comparing a single dispatch with a joint dispatch.

Figure 37 Presentation of the dispatch recommendation to BEMS.

4.4 Web Application as a stand-alone tool

To enhance usability, facilitate decision-making, and even allow the simulation of different scenarios, a web application was developed as a stand-alone tool, providing interactive simulations and performance visualizations based on the MILP optimization model. This platform allows users to analyse key metrics such as costs, emissions, and battery degradation, while configuring simulations based on different energy storage technologies.

The application enables users to customize and run simulations, comparing different battery technologies and hybrid storage solutions. Users can input expected load forecasts, market electricity prices, and battery characteristics to tailor the model to specific scenarios. The interface dynamically adjusts to reflect the impact of these inputs on system performance.

4.4.1 Key Functionalities of the Web Application

- Expected Load and Market Prices:

The simulator includes a structured table where users input hourly energy demand (kW) and market electricity prices (€/kWh), ensuring the model reflects realistic operational conditions. A screenshot of the corresponding section of the WebApp can be seen in Figure 38.

The screenshot shows a web application interface titled "Simulator" with the instruction "Choose one battery technology to simulate against a hybrid battery system combination of technologies!". It features two main input sections:

- Expected load forecast - kW:** A grid of 24 input fields for hourly load, with values ranging from 6 to 100.
- Expected day ahead market prices - €/kWh:** A grid of 24 input fields for hourly market prices, with values ranging from 1.02 to 4.64.

A "LOAD PARAMETERS" button is visible at the bottom left of the input area.

Figure 38 User interface of the battery simulation tool.

- Simulation Configuration:

Users begin by selecting a battery technology from a predefined list, which includes Lithium, Vanadium, Lead-Acid, Nickel-Cadmium, Sodium-Sulphur, Flywheels, and Supercapacitors. An option to add a second battery allows for hybrid energy system comparisons. The WebApp menu from which the user can make the selection is shown in Figure 39.

Figure 39 Possible types for battery presented in simulator.

- Parameter Input Fields:

Customization is available through input fields, where users define parameters such as maximum power capacity (kW), efficiency (%), and initial state of charge (SoC).

Users can then select between two objective functions—cost minimization and CO₂ emission reduction—guiding the MILP optimization engine to generate dispatch recommendations accordingly. The corresponding input fields can be seen in Figure 40.

Maximum power kW

Maximum capacity kWh

Efficiency %

Initial Soc %

SET PARAMETERS

Figure 40 Battery customization fields in simulation tool.

- Interactive Performance Visualizations:

The application features dynamic charts that graphically represent:

- Battery State of Charge (SoC): tracking the battery's energy levels over time.
- Dispatch Schedules: recommended energy dispatch plans for operational optimization.

These visualizations help users gain actionable insights into system behaviour and performance metrics. This can be seen in Figure 41.

Figure 41 Examples of single dispatch and a hybrid dispatch.

At the bottom of both plots, the tool shows the corresponding energy cost, the cost of degradation, and the total cost of dispatch, which corresponds to the sum of both. This appears for the single battery dispatch and hybrid dispatch, which allows for a direct comparison. Similarly, if the emissions minimization option is chosen, the tool will also show in the same fields the corresponding emissions (based on average values) from the energy consumption (from the grid), the carbon intensity corresponding to the degradation of the battery and the total emissions as the sum of both. This appears for the single battery dispatch and hybrid dispatch, which also allows for a direct comparison. The open-source InterSTORE WEB APP

allows further testing and validation of the model, demonstrating its potential for large-scale deployment.

The model can be tested in the following WebApp, which is open-source to the community at [INTERSTORE WEB APP](#).

5 Multi-physics Energy Management System

This chapter reports the implementation of interoperability and optimized control within a multi-physics behind-the-meter (BTM) system. The term "multi-physics" arises from the integration of DERs, specifically electric heat pumps (HPs), which couple the thermal and electrical energy domains. In pursuit of a low-carbon energy system, multi-physics systems that use synergies between energy vectors are gaining attention [15]. In this context, HPs are advantageous for low-emission heating due to their high efficiency and potential for flexibility. They can significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions and provide dynamic responses to energy demands, enhancing the overall efficiency and sustainability of energy systems. In 2024, the European Commission introduced the Heat Pump Accelerator Platform to boost heat pump adoption by uniting industry experts, policymakers, and stakeholders for collaboration and the exchange of best practices [16].

The content of this chapter is based on the energy management system (EMS) development task targeting the InterSTORE Project's "Use Case 8: Multiphysics flexibility optimization for Home Management Systems and their global integration." It is important to note that in earlier project documents submitted in the project acquisition stage, the targeted output of this task was referred to as a "residential power management system." However, the authors decided to adopt the term "multi-physics EMS" for two main reasons. Firstly, the EMS algorithms and interoperability implementation are designed to be application-agnostic, enhancing their reusability across different domains, whether residential, commercial, or industrial. Secondly, UC8 distinguishes itself from other InterSTORE EMS development use cases by incorporating DERs that couple the electrical system with other energy domains, such as heat. To emphasize this unique aspect, the term "multi-physics" has been preferred.

This chapter is organized as follows. Section 5.1 defines how the future generation of EMSs should perform (i.e., non-functional requirements) to optimally capture and utilize the flexibility of multi-physics energy systems. Based on the identified requirements, it proposes an energy management (EM) concept that allows for the implementation of two important EMS functions: (1) local control of behind-the-meter (BTM) multi-physics systems, and (2) remote monitoring of BTM assets for in-front-of-the-meter (FTM) utilization of the flexibility of these DERs. Section 5.2 explains how the core functional requirement (i.e., interoperability) can be implemented by using the InterSTORE interoperability concept over an example derived from the German pilot of the project. Section 5.3 introduces the proposed optimization process, illustrating how heat pumps are integrated into the local control EMS to maximize the energy self-sufficiency of a BTM system comprising multi-physics EMS.

5.1 Multi-physics energy management concept

The goal of concept development is to provide an easy-to-implement, replicable, and effective framework that can serve to capture and utilize the flexibility of multi-physics energy systems. The following sub-sections, respectively, define targeted qualities of future multi-physics EMS, propose a suitable EMS concept, and list the functional requirements (i.e., what the system must do) to realize the proposed concept.

5.1.1 Non-functional requirements

The multi-physics EMS concept should fulfil three non-functional requirements: versatility, dynamic adaptability, and computational performance.

Versatility is one of the critical non-functional requirements. In essence, the most suitable approach for implementing a multi-physics EMS can vary significantly depending on the asset combination, operational objectives, and stakeholder ecosystem. The asset combination can include the presence of other storage equipment and on-site generation, as well as the

type of multi-physics assets, such as air-to-water and water-to-water heat pumps. Operational objectives may differ, such as minimizing energy bills, maximizing local consumption of locally generated energy, or other specific goals. Additionally, the involved stakeholders can range from the owner of the BTM system to higher-level entities like aggregators and utilities that may require the flexibility of BTM assets to address FTM issues. The EM concept should cover a variety of scenarios.

Dynamic adaptability refers to the system's ability to adjust the behaviour of DERs in real-time to respond to variations in energy demand and supply. Without dynamic adaptability, the system becomes rigid and fails to optimize the utilization of its flexibility potential. This rigidity can lead to sub-optimal performance, as the system cannot respond effectively to real-time changes. For instance, if the system cannot adapt to fluctuating levels of renewable energy generation, it may miss opportunities to capitalize on periods of high renewable availability. This inability to adjust can result in continued reliance on non-renewable energy sources, thereby missing chances to enhance energy efficiency and environmental sustainability.

Computational performance is about the system's ability to process data and execute control algorithms efficiently and in a timely manner. High computational performance ensures that the EMS can handle large volumes of data from various DERs and respond to real-time changes in the energy landscape. This is particularly important for optimizing energy flows, managing the integration of renewable energy sources, and maintaining system stability. Poor computational performance can lead to delays in decision-making, reduced system responsiveness, and sub-optimal utilization of available resources.

5.1.2 Energy management concept

To address the above-mentioned non-functional requirements, an EM concept with the following characteristics is proposed:

1. *Distributed Computational Load:* The EM concept is designed to reduce the computational load by splitting tasks into two main categories, each conducted by dedicated hardware: real-time local control of BTM resources (EMS1 in Figure 42) and remote monitoring of BTM resources for potential FTM services (EMS2 in Figure 42). This division allows for more efficient processing and management of data in dedicated platforms. Furthermore, it can facilitate the implementation of cybersecurity approaches by featuring segmentation.
2. *Linear Analytical Tasks:* The concept consists of linear analytical tasks, including a *rule-based algorithm* that does not require the solution of complex non-linear optimization models. This approach simplifies the computational process and enhances system responsiveness to real-time situations. The local control algorithm, deployed in (EMS1) works in real-time, analysing the given state of the system and calculating set-points for DERs that will be valid only for a limited duration (e.g., 5 minutes). This ensures that the system can quickly adapt to changing conditions.

High-Level Reference Parameters: The local control algorithm consumes high-level reference parameters as inputs that are calculated a priori and represent the overarching system goal. Specifically, the algorithm receives reference SoC levels for storage assets, including both battery storage and thermal storage systems connected to the output of heat pumps. These reference parameters guide the real-time control actions to align with the overall system objectives.

The architecture for the implementation of the proposed concept is illustrated in Figure 42. In this architecture, EMS1 is responsible for monitoring the BTM DERs in real-time and assigning them set points (i.e., instructions for charging/discharging at decided power rates).

As indicated above, this algorithm is a rule-based algorithm –mathematical model to be presented in Operational optimization. EMS2 is responsible for aggregating the status of the DERs. In principle, an FTM platform owned by higher-level entities such as DSO, aggregator, or energy community operator can access this data. Likewise, the external platforms can set references that should/could be implemented by the FTM system owner.

Figure 42 Architecture of the energy management concept.

It is important to note that the envisioned EM concept, as illustrated in the above picture, allows for the implementation of various interoperability concepts based on different data models or communication technologies. However, the specific application reported in this work –the communication between BTM DERs and BTM Platform demonstrated in the German Pilot- implements the InterSTORE concept based on messages formatted according to IEEE2030.5 and communicated over NATS network. Section 5.2 details the implementation of interoperability (continuous arrows in Figure 42).

5.2 Interoperability implementation

In principle, the IEEE2030.5 standard enables structured messaging formats, enhancing interoperability and ensuring consistent data representation across diverse devices and platforms. However, at the time of conducting this work, no DERs at the campus of Research Center Jülich (FZJ) natively supported the IEEE2030.5 protocol. Similarly, the hardware from the Eaton substation automation platform product line, which was selected as the EMS platform to run real-time control and monitoring (referred to as EMS1 and EMS2 in the above figure in the German Pilot), was not compatible with IEEE2030.5. To address this challenge, the legacy protocol converter developed in the InterSTORE project was utilized in the architecture presented in Figure 43.

Figure 43 Presentation of LPC integration in Eaton architecture.

The deployed system includes two EMS hardware available energy automation solutions product lines of Eaton, with EMS1 – RT Control being Substation Automation Platform (SMP 4250) and EMS2 – RT Monitoring being SMP Gateway (SMP 3050) [17]. Both hardware types support several communication protocols such as IEC 61850 and GOOSE, DNP3, Modbus, IEC 60870-5-101/104 in the smart grid ecosystem and are traditionally deployed as remote terminal units in power system automation. However, SMP 4250 also features IEC 61131-3 Soft PLC and logic functions to implement a stand-alone power generating, distribution and storage system that can isolate itself from the primary utility grid and provide a reliable and efficient solution to unexpected power loss [18]. Both hardware offer Rest API to interact with external systems such as LPC. The multi-physics DERs –Riello battery and heat pump—in the pilot implement various communication protocols, and none of them is IEEE2030.5 native. However, by offering transformation between multiple protocols, LPC can enable integration of these devices into a communication system implemented using a NATS network and IEEE2030.5 data model.

For aforementioned reasons, the interoperability was achieved by deploying two LPCs between EMS and DER endpoints. In Figure 43, these are represented as LPC-EMS and LPC-DER. Each implements several transformations. To transmit the SoC of the battery and thermal energy storage (connected to the HP), aggregate electrical load and the net PV power generation, the LPC-DER has four specific transformation, each reading a particular message or Modbus register and publishing a structured NATS message in the LPC network (arrow between two LPCs in Figure 43). The LPC network includes a dedicated NATS server, acting as the central point to distribute messages formatted in IEEE2030.5 within the communication system to the correct end points. LPC-EMS essentially subscribes to the topics dedicated to informing EMS on DER status -in *DERStatus* and *MirrorMeteringList* formats- and transforms these messages to forms that can be read by APIs of EMS1 and EMS2. Upon

receiving the RT status of the DERs, the rule-based algorithm deployed in the SoftPLC module of the EMS1 determines the new set points of the controllable DERs, namely the heat pump and battery. These setpoints are read by the LPC-EMS, transformed into IEEE2030.5 data format *DERSetting*, and published in the NATS network under specified topics. The LPC-DER receives these messages under given topics and sends them to each DER's legacy communication system endpoints.

5.3 Operational optimization

This section outlines the EM algorithm designed for BTM systems consisting of electrical load, on-site PV generation, battery, and electrical HP. It is important to note that electrical HPs are not always installed with thermal energy storage (TES). However, at the time of conducting this work, combining HPs with TES was a usual practice. This is also the case for the pilot in FZJ, as shown in Figure 44, which also provided the specific multi-physics environment for implementation of the EM concept introduced in section 5.1. Here, the primary heat source is the low-temperature district heating (LTDH) network of the FZJ.

Figure 44 Schematic presentation of the pilot setup in Eaton use case. Taken from [19].

The primary function of the developed algorithm is to determine the real-time (RT) setpoints of the flexible/controllable DERs, namely HP and battery. The algorithm was designed in a way to optimize the electrical power injection/consumption provided by these devices with the purpose of increasing the energy autarky of the BTM system. It operates under a few assumptions and boundary conditions:

- *The coefficient of performance (COP) remains constant over a control horizon:* for this, the temperatures of the heat source (LTDH) and heat sink (water flowing into the condenser from TES) must remain constant. The gas boiler supplying thermal power to the LTDH network fulfils this condition for the source side. By selecting the control horizon (i.e., the duration for which the setpoints determined upon execution of the

algorithm will be implemented) sufficiently short (e.g., 5 minutes), it is also possible to keep the sink side temperature constant.

- *The thermal comfort in the building is secured, provided that the TES maintains a certain temperature.* As can be seen in Figure 44 the hot water that circulates in the pipes and radiators to deliver thermal energy to the building is only fed by the water tank, which practically behaves as the TES. The heat produced by the HP –or transferred from the heat source- enters the thermal power equation indirectly as the water heated by the HP flows into the water tank. Therefore, the HP's current operating point does not directly affect the current thermal comfort as long as the TES SoC remains at a decent level.
- *An a priori process – executed either by the EMS of BTM or the aggregator/utility-determines a SoC reference for the TES:* At any given time, the algorithm is fed with an input parameter (denoted by S_h in equations) that indicates the minimum SoC that the TES should have by the next time step (i.e., after implementing the decisions calculated by the algorithm during the whole control horizon). This parameter determines whether HP must charge (i.e., consume electrical power to transfer heat to TES) or not.
- The on-side generation, electrical load, battery SoC and TES SoC are accurately measured in RT and communicated over the system outlined in 5.2.

Under these assumptions, the algorithm aims to minimize the power exchanged with the main grid while prioritizing the maintenance of thermal comfort conditions in the building. In the following, this algorithm is formally introduced. Table 6 presents the list of parameters and control variables included in the algorithm.

Symbol	Description	Type - Source
ΔT	Control horizon	Parameter – Selected a priori
E_h	Energy Capacity of TES	Parameter – Device specification
E_b	Energy Capacity of Battery	Parameter – Device specification
η_b	Charge-/Discharge Efficiency of Battery	Parameter – Device specification
P_h^+	Maximum Electrical Power Input to HP	Parameter – Device specification
P_b^+	Maximum Charge Power to Battery	Parameter – Device specification
P_b^-	Maximum Discharge Power to Battery	Parameter – Device specification
S_h	TES SoC Reference L per Bunds	Parameter – Calculated a priori
η_h	Coefficient of Performance of HP	Parameter – Measured in RT
S_h	TES SoC of TES	Parameter – Measured in RT
S_b	SoC of Battery	Parameter – Measured in RT
P_L	Electrical loads	Parameter – Measured in RT
P_G	PV generation	Parameter – Measured in RT
p_h	Electrical power consumption of HP	Control variable
p_b	Electrical power consumption of Battery	Control variable

Table 6 List of parameters and control variables included in Eaton algorithm.

The execution of the multi-physics EM algorithm, as depicted in Table 7, starts by calculating the feasible operating ranges of the HP and battery for the considered control intervals (Steps 1-3). For the HP, the feasible range does not cover the “discharge” case, as a HP is essentially an electric power consumer. On the other hand, the battery can both charge (withdraw) and discharge (inject) electrical power.

Line	Calculation		
1	$\overline{P}_h = \text{MIN} \left(\frac{E_h \cdot (1 - S_h)}{\Delta T} \cdot \frac{1}{\eta_h}, P_h^+ \right)$		
2	$\overline{P}_b = \text{MIN} \left(\frac{E_b \cdot (1 - S_b)}{\Delta T}, P_b^+ \right)$		
3	$\underline{P}_b = \text{MIN} \left(\frac{E_b \cdot S_b}{\Delta T}, P_b^- \right)$		
4	IF	$S_h \leq \underline{S}_h$	
5		$\widetilde{P}_h = \frac{E_h \cdot (\underline{S}_h - S_h)}{\Delta T} \cdot \frac{1}{\eta_h}$	
6	ELSE		
7		$\widetilde{P}_h = 0$	
8		$P_{net} = P_L - P_G + \widetilde{P}_h$	
9	IF	$P_{net} < 0$	
10		IF	$P_{net} \leq \underline{P}_b \cdot \eta_b$
11			$p_b = -\frac{P_{net}}{\eta_b}$
12			$p_h = \widetilde{P}_h$
13		ELSE	
14			$p_b = \underline{P}_b$
15			$p_h = \widetilde{P}_h$
16	ELSE		
17		IF	$ P_{net} \leq \overline{P}_b$
18			$p_b = -P_{net} \cdot \eta_b$
19			$p_h = \widetilde{P}_h$
20		ELSE	
21			$p_b = \overline{P}_b$
22			$p_h = \text{MIN} \left(\widetilde{P}_h + P_{net} - \frac{p_b}{\eta_b}, \overline{P}_h \right)$

Table 7 Steps of operation feasibility calculation.

When calculating the upper bound of the feasible operation range of the HP—the maximum electrical power that the HP can withdraw at the given time, \overline{P}_h —, the additional thermal energy that the TES can accept is divided by ΔT to calculate the average thermal power that the TES would need to reach 100% SoC by the end of the control horizon; then this amount is mapped to electric power by division by the COP, η_h . However, this is a hypothetical case that may be infeasible due to the power capability of the HP. Therefore, in Line 1, the electrical power needed to charge the TES to 100% is compared with the maximum power of the HP to calculate the upper bound of the feasible range \overline{P}_h . Since HPs cannot retrieve electrical power lower, the lower bound of HP operation range is 0, and so it does not require a calculation. Lines 2 and 3 apply a similar logic to calculate the lower and upper bounds of battery operation range, with the exception that these calculations do not require mapping from thermal to electric domain with the help of the parameter COP.

This algorithm is designed in a way to prioritize the thermal comfort conditions in the building. This is achieved by keeping the TES SoC above \underline{S}_h . If the current SoC, S_h , is below this threshold, the HP must operate and charge the SoC to \underline{S}_h as indicated in Line 5 of the pseudo-code. In this algorithm, \widetilde{P}_h represents the desired operating point of the HP for the comfort conditions. If the comfort condition is already maintained with S_h being larger than \underline{S}_h , then the desired operating point would be set to 0 as in Line 7.

Unlike the HP, the batteries are not assigned with some SoC references in the demonstrated case. Therefore, the algorithm operates in a heat-driven manner; the heat pump contributes to the electrical power consumption by \widetilde{P}_h —see Line 8 for the net power consumption of the BTM system before the contribution of the battery— unless it is desired for the system to consume even more power than this (Line 22). The calculation of the setpoints is elaborated between Lines 7-21. As the algorithm aims at increasing the energy autarky, when the system has a power deficit ($P_{net} < 0$), the battery would be discharged to cover the deficit. Line 10 describes the case where the battery's current feasible operation range is sufficient to discharge enough power to cover the deficit of the system. In this case, the battery is assigned a set-point that covers the deficit such that the BTM internally balances the power consumption (Line 11). When the deficit is more significant, the battery is discharged at full power (Line 14). In both cases, the HP is operated at the comfort-safe power (\widetilde{P}_h). However, when the system still has power a surplus after inclusion of the power of the HP, the battery is instructed to charge. When the battery's power limit allows charging to fully cover the surplus (Line 17), the battery is charged only to the extent necessary. Otherwise, it is charged with full power, and the HP's power consumption is increased. The extent of this increase depends on the HP's power capability and the amount of residual surplus (Line 22).

6 EV hybrid distributed Energy Management System

In the present chapter are described the development activities performed to implement InterSTORE Energy Management System of Enel X and its inner working with the field assets in Enel X Roma LAB are described, as shown in the Figure 45.

In order to implement the UC9, some functions have been implemented in the EMS platform to be able to receive flexibility orders from the Flex platform and implement them by means of the assets connected.

Each individual flexibility resource does not hold adequate market value unless aggregated in the larger pool with capacity and characteristics that fulfil balancing services and market requirements.

The EMS is the system where the capabilities and the algorithms are implemented, based on data telemetry, which is collected from asset fields and used to feed the algorithm and calculate the flexibility availability.

In this way, each resource can contribute to grid service markets as part of a VPP (Virtual Power Plant), despite having different power profiles and capabilities (capacity, time constraints, response, and ramp times).

Figure 45 E2E Architecture in RM XLAB for DR event

6.1 Interoperability toolkit

Client-Server library developed in the Legacy Protocol Converter software [9] [8] will be a starting point for achieving interoperability that IEEE2030.5 over NATS offers.

Based on this library, Enel X will implement the Flexibility use case using the LPC gateway that will put in communication the Energy Management System (EMS) with diverse typologies and sizes of assets (PVs, Storages of different sizes and brands, Vehicle-to-grid (V2G) EVs). Schneider assets (XWpro Inverter) have implemented and manage IEEE2030.5 protocol.

6.1.1 Development steps

Next, in Table 8 are presented steps that were taken for reaching the objective of natively communicating via IEEE2030.5 over NATS:

Number	Step	Description	Constraints
1	Install the LPC open-source Library on GitHub.	LPC SW manages protocol translation: the specific attributes were inspected for each flow to be managed.	Different protocol management assets speaking in Modbus and assets speaking in IEEE2030.5.
2	Install Client/server open-source software on GitHub.	The Gateway has acted as a server to be compliant with IEEE2030.5 specs: the server starts the request to the Asset that acts as a client IEEE2030.5.	In the procedure, an HTTP connection should be implemented with a secure TLS connection to be compliant with IEEE2030.5 spec.
3	Create Mapping Modbus /IEEE2030.5 and IEEE2030.5 /MQTT.	Creation of the variable mapping in the Modbus and IEEE2030.5 case.	
4	Creating and Configuring GW.	Based on the mapping and rules set up, we generate software (with Docker engine and compose) that will do the conversion automatically.	Docker SW has been installed on the XLAB PC.
5	Adding the LPC Gateway in EnelX infrastructure: GW integration with EMS platform via the IoT Platform.	To implement GW integration in the EMS platform, an Infocert certification management was required in LPC GW.	To connect to the IoT platform, a cybersecurity requirement had to be fulfilled (infocert certificate exchange between the LPC GW and ENX IoT platform).
6	GW entity has to be created in ENX IoT platform.	LPC GW has been updated to handle 1) GW registration in IoT platform and 2) allowing asset creation with a Thing number (TAG)	In order to connect to ENX IoT platform, the registration procedure should be followed.
7	Integration IEEE2030.5 server GW with IEEE2030.5 Client (ASSET).	Implementation of IEEE2030.5 client-server SW to manage the integration with IEEE2030.5 asset. Mandatory requirement is an HTTP connection and TLS connection with Sunspec exchange certificate.	IEEE2030.5 protocol requires an HTTP - TLS connection with Sunspec certificate exchange.
8	Test of Telemetries messages conversion and ingestion on IoT platform.	Messages with telemetry from the assets are converted into MQTT protocol to go to EMS platform via IoT platform.	
9	Implementation of commands (power setpoint) from EMS to the assets.	Capability to send commands to the device. IoT will write the command (Jason format) on MQTT specific topic to which the LPC gateway will be subscribed for reading. As soon as a message comes, LPC needs to translate the message in IEEE2030.5 /Modbus and send it to the field assets.	

Table 8 Development steps for interoperability in ENX.

Step 1 - Step 2: First step consists of connecting to <https://github.com/Horizont-Europe-Interstore/> and installing:

- Interoperable Client/Server for IEEE2030.5 communication between devices and EMS systems
- Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) software V1.2.0 on PC control room XLAB.

Step 3 - Step 4: Mapping the variable for each asset:

- For the assets supporting Modbus protocol, creating variables mapping Modbus/IEEE2030.5
- Create mapping variables from IEEE2030.5/MQTT
- For Asset supporting IEEE2030.5 protocol create mapping from IEEE2030.5/MQTT
- YML file is generated and launched for each asset (thing) to create the telemetry flow to the IT platforms

Step 5 - Step 6: Integrating LPC GTW in IoT platform: to integrate the LPC gateway in ENX IoT platform, Sunesis has developed functionalities 1) to manage Infocert certificate and secure connection; 2) registration Phase in order to manage the Object Thing identifier of the asset. In compliance with IoT platform specs (Third party integration), the gateway had to register on the IoT platform, generating an Infocert certificate and Key to be authorized to be connected to the IoT platform.

Step 7: The Client/server gateway will be set in order to integrate the server IEEE2030 with the client, able to interwork with IEEE Schneider assets.

Step 8: The LPC SW has been launched, and telemetries are received by EMS in order to build the historical behaviour of the asset and feed the algorithms implemented in the system.

Step 9: Once the sites are defined on EMS and telemetries come to the system the algorithm can run and execute the Flexibility service request coming from Flex platform. The disaggregation events can be executed in order to send the single command to the single asset belonging to the aggregated site.

6.1.2 Time plan of development

The development steps were done by Enel X Lab Team and IT Team starting in May of 2024 (after first versions of client/server was released in the project) and finished in two steps: first part in December 2024 for the first flow collecting telemetries from Modbus Assets and second part in February 2025 with LPC improvement to handle telemetries from IEEE2030.5 assets and the second flow implementation DR event from IT platform to Assets. A detailed schematic plan can be seen on Figure 46.

Figure 46 Development time plan for ENX.

6.2 Flexibility service Implementation

In order to include the management of DERs in the Energy Management system, a series of preparatory activities is required to configure the system for the orchestration of the service

to different types of testing sites. To this end, we explain below the components that make up the system. Following is the EMS Functional high-level design architecture on Figure 47:

Figure 47 High-level EMS architecture.

As per the above figure, a new component, “InterSTORE Dispatcher,” has been developed. In the site controller, there is embedded the LPC and IEEE2030.5 client-server software are embedded.

The “Der Group Optimizer Orchestrator” has been enhanced with the new algorithm implementation.

The following are the detailed EMS development steps taken in InterSTORE project:

- New entities definition in EMS (Storages/Inverter/PV panels/CS)
- Calculation of flexibility provisioning
- Integration with "solcast" for solar production prediction
- Algorithm development
- Command manager component to dispatch commands
- Feedback and monitoring

6.2.1 New entities definition in EMS

Firstly, a report on all the entities/functional modules that should be defined and enrolled in EMS in order to fulfil the requested Use Case is listed. In the Table 9 The new DERs that have been configured in EMS (BESSs and PV plant). The Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment (EVSE) is already present in the system.

Development steps	Summary
BESS management	New Asset entity definition BESS. BESS creation, update, configuration, and deletion.
BESS data ingestion	Preparation of different data acquisition providers. Development focused on the Enel X - IoT layer.
BESS commands definition	Sending of control command towards the BESS by means of Enel X - IoT layer.
Solar Plant Management	New asset entity definition: Solar plant. Solar Plant creation, update, configuration, and deletion. Solar Plant adding/removing to/from a BESS
BESS enrolment	The DR participation is made by adding the BESS to an asset group that participates in a contract program. DR Reporting is impacted to include the BESS contribution.
DR Optimization with BESS	In a Load Area with Charging Stations and no optimization activated, the BESS participation in a DR Event must be optimized by calculating the best control plan for the BESS.

Table 9 Development steps for the new entity definition.

Following is the list of attributes for the new entity of BESS, developed and stored in Table 10.

Attribute Name	Description	Mandatory	UOM	Type field
BESS Name	The name of the BESS	Y		string
BESS SN	Serial number of the BESS	N		string
Brand	The brand of the BESS	Y		List
Model	The model of the BESS	Y		List
Type	The type of BESS (Enum with types mapping to be provided)	N		ENUM
Minimum SoC	Hard constrain defined at low level, when the BESS reach this level it won't be possible to discharge more	Y	%	Number
Maximum SoC	Hard constrain defined at low level, when the BESS reach this level it won't be possible to charge any more	Y	%	Number
Address	The address where the BESS is located	Y		string
Nominal Capacity	The nominal capacity of the BESS	Y	Wh	Number
Max Power	Max power in charging/discharging mode	N	W	
Telemetry Provider	Drop down list. (for now): IoT Platform Aurora's Grid - For next epic Direct REST connection (foxess) - For next epic DER.OS - For next epic	Y	-	ENUM
Status	the status of the BESS: ONLINE/OFFLINE			ENUM

Thing ID	The ID of the BESS's gateway on IoT platform	N	-	string
Operative Mode	This value represents the operating mode of the BESS. This is the Two possible option should be available Bypass: this means that all the information coming from the BESS will be ignored UPS - Power Backup	Y	-	ENUM
Controllable	Boolean to indicate if the BESS is controllable or not.			boolean
TenantId	The tenant			string
charging need	An object containing the charging needs of the BESS: min SoC, target SoC, time of target SoC (see table below).	N	-	Object
Offline-Behaviour	The behaviour of the BESS in offline (To be clarified).	N		ENUM
Offline-Power	The current of the BESS in charging/discharging while offline.	N	W	Number
Advanced parameters	An array of objects (parameter name, uom, value) that is specific for the brand/model.	Y		array
gridHierarchy	An object describing the inverter position with respect to the grid and/or the PV plant.	N		Object

Table 10 BESS attributes were added during the development.

Following is Table 11, in which the Object Charging needs are reported for a BESS (each BESS must contain the constraints that are respected by implementing the command plan):

Field Name	Description	Mandatory	UOM	Type field
min SoC (user-defined)	Value of charge under which the BESS is never supposed to go; it has to be greater than the minimum SoC defined by the vendor	No, in case it is not defined, use the minimum SoC of the vendor.	%	Int
max SoC (user defined)	Value of charge over which the BESS is never supposed to go; it has to be lower than the max SoC defined by the vendor.	No, in case it is not defined, use the min SoC of the vendor.	%	Int
max energy per year	Max yearly energy from the grid.	The maximum energy that can be absorbed from the grid by the BESS per year.	kWh/Year	Number
max energy per day	Max daily energy from the grid.	The maximum energy that can be	kWh/day	Number

		absorbed from the grid by the BESS per day.		
load	The building load associated with the BESS.	N		string
pv	The PV plant is associated with the BESS.	N		string

Table 11 Object Charging needs and the object's grid hierarchy.

6.2.2 Calculation of Flexibility provision

Enel X is an Energy Service Provider (ESP) and, for that, it needs to be able to monitor its aggregated pool and, in particular, have a good forecast of flexibility possibilities by its arbitrary group in the disaggregation logic of a DR event. To obtain such a calculation:

- The system shall perform calculations to determine the best actions for flexibility provision, considering the current state and capabilities of the assets.
- Calculation Parameters: Asset SoC, energy demand, forecasted energy production
- Forecast input for disaggregation logic.

When a solar panel is included in the arbitrary group and a DR event is sent to the arbitrary group, the algorithm needs to take into account the solar production forecast of that specific PV, which will be associated with a controllable resource (BESS or Charging Station) of the load area. As a consequence, the disaggregation of the DR event between the single controllable devices in the arbitrary group will be able to follow the logic of maximisation of self-consumption.

6.2.3 Integration with "solcast" for solar production prediction

The forecast of solar panel production in a given area is based on meteorological variables. Meteorological variables can be retrieved from numerical weather prediction models (i.e. GFS, ECMWF). Afterwards, the Forecast Engine should be capable of estimating the deviation to optimise and adjust the prediction. The forecast should cover at least the calculation time horizon used by the site optimiser.

Forecast should be able to predict PV Rooftop power for each PV Panel group, which defines the PV Plant (i.e. PV Plant configured with 7 PV Panel oriented South-East and 0° tilt and 7 PV Panel oriented South-West with 35° of tilt).

6.2.4 Algorithm development

In EMS, the optimizations are managed through computational algorithms that take as input a series of parameters related to the site topology and constraints (customer constrain) in addition to user preferences and give as output the power profile that the controllable asset must follow in the next 24 hours: control plan for EVSE and load plan for BESS.

For InterSTORE project, the offer of optimisation services is enriched with load balancing extended to BESS (the EVSE load balancing was already implemented). The algorithm is enriched with the capability of disaggregating a DR event into groups of mixed controllable assets formed by BESS and/or BESS + EVSE (V2G).

The developments performed on EMS for the Algorithms are implemented in the following libraries:

Minimum package versions supporting InterSTORE:

- dantzig 3.41.1
- dream 1.3.1
- dantzigsim-gen 0.8.0

The implemented macro-functions are:

- Site Modelling and Optimisation Algorithm.
- Site control Algorithm.
- Disaggregation event.
- Check DR Feasibility.

A more detailed description for each one will follow.

6.2.1.1 Site modelling and optimisation algorithm

Preparation of the pilot site was needed in order to prepare the basic structure on which developed approaches can be tested and observed in a real-world environment. The following two possible configurations were prepared:

- Configuration with one hybrid inverter (PV + BESS + load), shown on Figure 48

Figure 48 Configuration with one hybrid inverter (PV + BESS + load).

- Configuration with separated inverter (2) (for PV and BESS + load), shown on Figure 49.

Figure 49 -Configuration with a separate inverter (for PV and BESS + load).

The setups in the figures above represent the supported site topologies implemented at customer sites. The squares in the figure are the physical objects (PV, Storage, EV) and each one, as it is added to the graph (and also shown in Figure 50), brings the constraints related to that object into the optimisation problem. The dotted circles add the objectives that need to be achieved with the site control, such as:

- Charging needs of the EVs
- Self-consumption at POD (or POI) level
- Execute the power set points required by the flexibility service.

Figure 50 Schematic presentation of ENX EMS algorithm on an example site.

6.2.1.2 Site control algorithm

Once the site has been defined and configured, and information is provided to all the elements about constraints/objectives, the algorithm is run, and as a result, the algorithm provides the power set points for the EV chargers and for the inverters for each previously configured site.

The purpose of the dream library (version 1.3.1) is to process the information from a set of sites and compute the setpoint of each in order to satisfy a front-of-the-meter event.

An event applies to a set of sites. Each site is composed of a set of assets. Within each site, the event can apply to:

- All the assets of a site (in which case we say that the POI asset participates to the event)
- Only a subgroup of assets within a site

The dream library allows processing the information from all sites in a decentralised way and then performs a centralised step for aggregation. How aggregation and decentralisation are coordinated and what information is considered in the process depends on the chosen strategy.

Independent of the strategy, we can identify two main steps.

6.2.1.3 Disaggregation event

Once a set of sites and a DR event have been defined (with an indication of the interval time and minimum and maximum power), the algorithm divides the PMax and PMin on the individual sites, taking into account both the physical constraints and the objectives that each site has (if a site needs a greater energy demand in a certain time interval, it will be assigned a lesser constraint on the PMax).

This is performed by the *dream.functions.aggregate* function for every site participating in the event. In general, the function can be called in parallel for all sites and the results collected later, which allows for complete decentralization, as aggregate can be called by a local server or by any microservice. Required inputs for said function are a specific Aggregation Input, the dantzig registration and optimization payloads. Aggregation input is about specifying the information about the event, about chosen strategy, about the way the site is controlled, and about the subgroup of assets participating in the event. The function output depends heavily on the chosen strategy.

Later *dream.functions.disaggregate* function is called afterwards. Required input is a specific Disaggregation input, where it is specified the information about the event, the chosen strategy, and all the aggregation results from the previous step. The function output depends on the chosen strategy: if the algorithm specified in the strategy has converged, the output will be a set-point for each subgroup participating in the event; if the algorithm has not converged, the aggregation/disaggregation steps must be repeated.

6.2.1.4 Check DR feasibility

After each site optimization, the *check_dr_feasibility* function must be invoked, given as input the POI power, which was taken from the POI AVG_POWER control in the output payload. Since the POI shows positive power when exporting to the grid and negative power when importing from the grid, a sign convention opposite to the DR event convention is applied. Similarly, the POI power sign must be reversed before being passed to the *check_dr_feasibility* function.

6.2.5 Command manager

The task of the Command Manager is to control remote devices through the mechanism of the IoT shadow.

When a ControlPlan is received, the Command Manager creates schedules for each setpoint in the ControlPlan (sending gRPC calls to the Scheduler). The scheduler will then send back a pulse to the Command Manager with the setpoint ID to apply. The Command Manager transforms the setpoint information into a desired shadow state and sends it to the device. The microservice also exposes REST APIs for sending shadows.

6.2.6 Feedback and monitoring

The system shall provide feedback on the execution of the dispatch order and monitor the performance of the assets during the flexibility events.

Monitoring Metrics: Energy curtailed, asset performance, compliance with dispatch orders.

The data of the events is sent to the Flex platform to be used for the settlement process and should be stored in the EMS database for further analysis and to be shared in the Dataspace connector as explained in D4.2.

7 Conclusions

The developments undertaken in WP4 were not always straightforward and sometimes required a few minor deviations. The most noticeable change was in the EMS architecture plan, or in downgrading the initial plan, as the primary goal could not be presented in the pilot. Other limitations included the inflexibility of the hardware used to comply with the actual working plan and the security risks posed by exposing the secure IoT architecture of partners to the public internet.

Considering all of the above, the time spent on development is understandable. The participants of WP4 monitored the development progress and received updates during regular monthly check-up calls. The status of each segment was marked in accordance with a colour scale presented in Figure 51. Each task began in orange (planning phase) and progressed to yellow (discussion phase), then blue (development phase), and lastly green (finished - production phase).

Figure 51 Colourscale showing status of development.

On Figure 52 the development progress of each task can be observed over the months.

Figure 52 Specific development task per partner in WP4.

In the last months of WP4, the focus of partners shifted from EMS development to presenting new approaches in pilots. These demonstrations require good coordination between pilot site preparation tasks (such as understanding pilot requirements and specifications, implement-

ing required HW and SW) and the development of EMS. Each partner has managed this coordination successfully, as at the end of WP4, all pilots are already live. Pilot site preparation is, however, still not finalised and will continue a few months after the conclusion of WP4.

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LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 CyberGrid's stepwise plan towards interoperability.....	15
Table 2 CyberGrid's steps toward connection over open data spaces.....	17
Table 3 steps of development for hybridisation tools.....	19
Table 4 development steps for the market arbitrage tools.....	22
Table 5 Development steps for the energy community toolkit.....	24
Table 6 List of parameters and control variables included in Eaton algorithm.....	52
Table 7 Steps of operation feasibility calculation.....	53
Table 8 Development steps for interoperability in ENX.....	56
Table 9 Development steps for the new entity definition.....	59
Table 10 BESS attributes were added during the development.....	60
Table 11 Object Charging needs and the object's grid hierarchy.....	61

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 Four pilot sites in InterSTORE.....	11
Figure 2 Workflow in InterSTORE project among WPs.	12
Figure 3 Time plan of client/server integration in CyberNoc.	16
Figure 4 Connections towards DER in Austrian pilot.	16
Figure 5 Time plan of client/server integration in CyberNoc.	17
Figure 6 Offered service from the energy community and CyberGrid.....	18
Figure 7 Presentation of SoC management UI in CyberNoc.	19
Figure 8 Schematics of the PID controller logic integrated in CyberNoc.....	20
Figure 9 Time plan of the hybridization approaches in CyberNoc.....	21
Figure 10 Presentation of the market arbitrage tool in CyberNoc.....	23
Figure 11 Time plan of the market arbitrage tool development in CyberNoc.	23
Figure 12 Presentation of actions and steps in the energy community toolkit.....	24
Figure 13 Time plan of the Energy Community toolkit integration in CyberNoc.....	25
Figure 14 Time plan of the HyDEMS development, considering its interoperability toolkit.....	26
Figure 15 DERs interface used for UC7 in GridLab.....	27
Figure 16: One level hybridization scheme.	28
Figure 17 Generic scheme of hybridization of different technologies.	29
Figure 18 Scheme example of three different technologies.	29
Figure 19 Inputs/Outputs SoF function.	30
Figure 20 SoF dimensionless vector for each system.	32
Figure 21 Example of the developed SoF calculation for 16 h.....	33
Figure 22 Schematic of the developed scenario of UC7 in Gridlab Valencia.....	33
Figure 23 The log files from the implemented HyDEMS with LPC in GridLab Spain pilot.	34
Figure 24 DER1 GridLab scenario for synchronization test.....	34
Figure 25 Full DER1 synchronization test: synchronizer OFF in island, then Synchronizer is ON, switched to the grid-connected mode after synchronization.....	35
Figure 26 Power profile generated by PSC4.	36
Figure 27 Power profile generated by PSC3 for firming test.	36
Figure 28 Power Real-time interface of the HESS DER1 system response during VI event.	37
Figure 29 Power Real time interface of the HESS DER1 system response during firming event.	37
Figure 30 Current contribution of HESS system in DER1 – Hybridization of BESS and UCAP.	38
Figure 31 SoF values during test events, VI and Firming with LPC.	38
Figure 32. Real time monitoring demonstration of VI and Firming at HESStec.	39
Figure 33 Connection architecture between the systems.	40
Figure 34 The log files from the LPC in the Portuguese pilot.	41
Figure 35 Examples of the day-ahead prices (a) and emissions (b) for a given day.	42
Figure 36 Example of a load forecast generated by the HEMS microservice.	43
Figure 37 Presentation of the dispatch recommendation to BEMS.	43
Figure 38 User interface of the battery simulation tool.	44
Figure 39 Possible types for battery presented in simulator.....	44
Figure 40 Battery customization fields in simulation tool.....	45
Figure 41 Examples of single dispatch and a hybrid dispatch.....	45
Figure 42 Architecture of the energy management concept.....	49
Figure 43 Presentation of LPC integration in Eaton architecture.	50
Figure 44 Schematic presentation of the pilot setup in Eaton use case. Taken from [19].	51
Figure 45 E2E Architecture in RM XLAB for DR event.....	55
Figure 46 Development time plan for ENX.	57
Figure 47 High-level EMS architecture.	58
Figure 48 Configuration with one hybrid inverter (PV + BESS + load).....	62

Figure 49 Configuration with a separate inverter (for PV and BESS + load).63
Figure 50 Schematic presentation of ENX EMS algorithm on an example site.63
Figure 51 Colourscale showing status of development.66
Figure 52 Specific development task per partner in WP4.66